

SATISFACTORY

Project Acronym: **SatisFactory**
Project Full Title: **A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments**
Grant Agreement: **636302**
Project Duration: **36 months (01/01/2015 - 31/12/2017)**

DELIVERABLE D5.2.1

Evaluation Methodology and Plans

Deliverable Status: **Final**
File Name: **SatisFactory-D5.2-Evaluation Methodology and Plans.pdf**
Due Date: **February 2016 (M14)**
Submission Date: **February 2016 (M14)**
Task Leader: **ABE (T5.2)**

Dissemination level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°636302

The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

¹ Project Coordinator

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author (Editor)				
Surname		First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
Vamvalis		Cosmas	ATLANTIS	vamvalis@abe.gr
Co-authors (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Arena	Damiano	EPFL	damiano.arena@epfl.ch
2	Cultrona	Pietro Alberto	COMAU	pietro.cultrona@comau.com
3	Jentsch	Marc	FIT	marc.jentsch@fit.fraunhofer.de
4	Kanidis	Stefanos	SUNLIGHT	s.kanidis@sunlight.gr
5	Krinidis	Stelios	CERTH	krinidis@iti.gr
6	Parcharidis	Symeon	SUNLIGHT	s.parcharidis@sunlight.gr
7	Pulizzotto	Alessio	COMAU	Alessio.pulizzotto@comau.com
8	Rusinà	Fulvio	COMAU	Fulvio.rusina@comau.com
9	Serra	Antonio	REGOLA	a.serra@regolat.it
10	Vlachogiannis	Evangelos	FIT	evangelos.vlachogiannis@fit.fraunhofer.de
11	Voutetakis	Spyros	CERTH	paris@cperi.certh.gr
12	Ziogou	Chrysovalantou	CERTH	czilogou@cperi.certh.gr

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Della Casa	Emiliano	GlassUp	
2	Sottile	Francesco	ISMB	
3	Vergori	Paolo	ISMB	

REVISION CONTROL

Version	Author	Date	Status
0.01	Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE)	January 12, 2016	Initial Draft, ToC
0.02	Kanidis Stefanos (Sunlight) Metaxa Ifigeneia (ABE) Nunzio Damiano Arena (EPFL) Parcharidis Symeon (Sunlight) Rusinà Fulvio (COMAU) Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE) Voutetakis Spyros (CERTH) Ziougou Chrysovalantou (CERTH)	January 22, 2016	ToC revision, Objectives, ISO and EOCGRAI methodologies, evaluation criteria, Pilot sites description, GES approach
0.03	Jentsch Marc (FIT) Metaxa Ifigeneia (ABE)	February 1, 2016	Evaluation Methodologies, Questionnaires for Workers
0.04	Krinidis Stelios (CERTH) Metaxa Ifigeneia (ABE)	February 2, 2016	Evaluation Process
0.05	Cultrona Pietro Alberto (COMAU) Krinidis Stelios (CERTH) Metaxa Ifigeneia (ABE) Nunzio Damiano Arena (EPFL) Parcharidis Symeon (Sunlight) Pulizzotto Alessio (COMAU) Serra Antonio (Regola) Ziougou Chrysovalantou (CERTH)	February 9, 2016	Evaluation Scenarios and Evaluation Tests, KPIs from end users, Objectives update, Pilot sites description update, Questionnaires for decision-makers
0.06	Jentsch Marc (FIT) Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE)	February 16, 2016	Evaluation Scenarios and Evaluation Tests,
0.07	Jentsch Marc (FIT) Nunzio Damiano Arena (EPFL) Serra Antonio (Regola) Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE) Ziougou Chrysovalantou (CERTH)		Criteria update, critical KPIs, Introduction, Instruments, Conclusions, Evaluation Scenarios and Evaluation Tests
0.08	Krinidis Stelios (CERTH) Nunzio Damiano Arena (EPFL) Serra Antonio (Regola) Turinetto Maurizio (Regola)		KPIs refinement, Questionnaires template, Impact Check List update, Evaluation Tests update

SATISFACTORY

	Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE) Vlachogiannis Evangelos (FIT)		
0.09	Krinidis Stelios (CERTH) Serra Antonio (Regola) Turinetto Maurizio (Regola) Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE) Vlachogiannis Evangelos (FIT)		Evaluation Tests and Questionnaires update, Submitted for review
0.10	Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE)		Quality Check
0.11	Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE)		Final Draft reviewed
1.0	Vamvalis Cosmas (ABE)		Submission to the EC

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Figures	9
List of Tables	10
List of Definitions & Abbreviations	11
Executive Summary	12
1. Introduction	13
2. SatisFactory Evaluation Framework	14
2.1 Objectives of the Evaluation	14
2.2 Evaluation Methodology and Criteria	16
2.2.1 Human-centric Evaluation Methodology	16
2.2.1.1 Evaluation Approaches for First Iterations	17
2.2.1.2 Final Evaluation Approaches	19
2.2.2 ECOGRAI Evaluation Methodology	21
2.2.2.1 Phase 0: Modelling of the Production System Control Structure and Identification of the PCC	23
2.2.2.2 Phase 1: Identification of the PCC Objectives and Coherence Analysis	23
2.2.2.3 Phase 2: Identification of the PCC Drivers and analysis of the conflicts	24
2.2.2.4 Phase 3: Identification of the PCC PIs and Internal Coherence Analysis	24
2.2.2.5 Phase 4: Design of the PI Information System	24
2.2.2.6 Phase 5: Integration of the Performance Indicator information system in the Production information system	25
2.2.3 Combined Evaluation Methodology	26
2.2.4 Evaluation Criteria	26
2.2.4.1 Usability	26
2.2.4.2 Knowledge Integration	27
2.2.4.3 Perception of working experience	27
2.2.4.4 User acceptance	27
2.2.4.5 Impact of SatisFactory	28
2.2.5 Performance Indicators	29
2.2.5.1 Usability	29
2.2.5.2 Knowledge Integration	29
2.2.5.3 Perception of working experience	30
2.2.5.4 User acceptance	31
2.2.5.5 Impact of SatisFactory	31
3. SatisFactory Pilot Sites (Area Analysis and Design)	33
3.1 CERTH/CPERI	33
3.1.1 Description of selected pilot areas	33
3.1.2 Legal and Operational Constraints	34
3.2 SUNLIGHT	34
3.2.1 Description of selected pilot areas	34
3.2.2 Legal and Operational Constraints	37
3.3 COMAU	38
3.3.1 Description of selected pilot areas	38

3.3.2	Legal and Operational Constraints	40
4.	Evaluation Process	42
4.1	Evaluation Scenarios (ES)	42
4.1.1	Evaluation Scenario ES1: Supporting Assembly Operations	42
4.1.1.1	ES1.1 Automated support for assembly operations	42
4.1.1.2	ES1.2 AR supported assembly operations	43
4.1.2	Evaluation Scenario ES2: Offering Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing Services	43
4.1.2.1	ES2.1 Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	44
4.1.2.2	ES2.2 Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	44
4.1.3	Evaluation Scenario ES3: Supporting Incident Detection & Recognition Operations	44
4.1.3.1	ES3.1: Supporting Cell Temperature Incidents During Jar Formation	45
4.1.3.2	ES3.2: Recognizing Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor	45
4.1.4	Evaluation Scenario ES4: Offering “On-the-Job” Training Services	46
4.1.4.1	ES4.1 Training environment set-up	46
4.1.4.2	ES4.2 Training support – Execution	46
4.1.4.3	ES4.3 Training support – Data Analysis	47
4.1.5	Evaluation Scenario ES5: Gamification and Collaboration Tools Usage	48
4.1.5.1	ES5.1: Gamification Tools Usage	48
4.1.5.2	ES5.2: Collaboration Tools Usage	48
4.2	Evaluation Planning	49
4.2.1	Evaluation Workshops	49
4.2.1.1	1 st Evaluation Workshop (M15-16)	50
4.2.1.2	2 nd Evaluation Workshop (M23-M24)	51
4.2.1.3	3 rd Evaluation Workshop (M31-M32)	51
4.2.2	Instruments	52
	Conclusions	53
	References	54
	Annexe I: Questionnaire for Workers	55
	Questionnaire ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Workers)	58
	Questionnaire ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Workers)	60
	Questionnaire ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (Workers)	62
	Questionnaire ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (Workers)	64
	Questionnaire ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT (Workers)	66
	Questionnaire ET6.1 MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (Workers)	68
	Questionnaire ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (Workers)	70
	Questionnaire ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Workers)	72
	Questionnaire ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT (Workers)	74
	Annexe II: Questionnaire for Decision Makers	76

Questionnaire ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Decision Makers)	78
Questionnaire ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Decision Makers)	80
Questionnaire ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (Decision Makers)	82
Questionnaire ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (Decision Makers)	84
Questionnaire ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT (Decision Makers)	86
Questionnaire ET6.2 MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (Decision Makers)	88
Questionnaire ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (Decision Makers)	90
Questionnaire ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (Decision Makers)	92
Questionnaire ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT (Decision Makers)	94
Annexe III: Impact Check List	96
IMPACT CHECK LIST 1 (Workers)	97
IMPACT CHECK LIST 2 (Decision Makers)	99
Annex IV: Evaluation Tests	101
Evaluation Test ET1: Automated support for Assembly Operations	101
Evaluation Test ET2: AR supported Assembly Operations	103
Evaluation Test ET3: Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	106
Evaluation Test ET4: Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	108
Evaluation Test ET5: Collaboration in Shop Floor Working environment	110
Evaluation Test ET6: Monitor Jar Formation Operation (detection of either manually driven or real incidents)	112
Evaluation Test ET7: Recognition of Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor	114
Evaluation Test ET8: On-the-Job Training in Assembly Operations	116
Evaluation Test ET9: Gamification in Shop Floor Working Environment	119

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Evaluation Objectives.....	15
Figure 2 The six steps of the ECOGRAI method.....	22
Figure 3 CERTH/CPERI shop floor view.....	33
Figure 4 Battery formation modules with Acid circulation	35
Figure 5 Sunlight Motive Power Battery	36
Figure 6 Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line	36
Figure 7 Robot wrist assembly	39
Figure 8 Body Assembly	40
Figure 9 World Class Manufacturing program pillars.....	41

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Specification Sheet for PI of the ECOGRAI method	25
--	----

LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AREA	Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance
BS	Business Scenario
BSC	Business Scenarios
CMMS	Computerised Maintenance Management System
DoW	Description of Work
DV	Decision Variables
EC	European Commission
EIS	Executive Information System
ES	Evaluation Scenario
EU	European Union
iDSS	Integrated Decision Support System
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PCC	Principle Control Centers
PI	Performance Indicators
PIS	Performance Indicator Systems
PMS	Production Management Systems
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
UCD	User Centred Design

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020).

The goal of this deliverable is to report on the SatisFactory Evaluation Methodology and Plans that are being developed in the scope of Task T5.2 ("Evaluation Methodology and Plans").

The goal of this deliverable is to prepare the evaluation methodology, plan and tools foreseen in the project, providing an evaluation framework for adequately assessing the level of fulfilment of the project objectives and the value of its results in terms of their appreciation by the factory workers and the decision makers. It is noted that Task 5.2 (and D5.2) are related with activities of T1.3 Use cases and Scenarios, T5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case, T5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators and T5.5 Evaluation, Results consolidation and Lessons learned. In order to achieve this goal specific evaluation scenarios and tests are defined that will enable reporting measurable results for the evaluation of the overall SatisFactory framework, covering all functionalities and identified business scenarios.

The evaluation framework is described, starting with the objectives which are presented along with the methodology and deriving criteria. After that, the Key Performance Indicators that will be used for the evaluation are given, following the structure of the defined criteria. It should be mentioned here that the overall approach serves three purposes: i) the evaluation of the performance of the components from the end users point of view, ii) the workers' satisfaction following the user-centred approach, iii) the overall SatisFactory framework performance. Moreover, a short description of the Pilot sites is provided, pointing out any legal and operational constraints that need to be considered in the process.

The specific evaluation tests to be performed in order to address the defined evaluation scenarios, along with the corresponding evaluation metrics which will be utilized per test for the extraction of measurable results as well as, the evaluation plan to be followed during pilot realization for tests execution, are described in Chapter 4. Additionally, the concept of the evaluation workshops and information session is presented, along with their time schedule for user experience evaluation. The dedicated questionnaires which have been prepared to are provided in the annexes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The scope of the SatisFactory evaluation framework that has been set up is to allow the evaluation of the outcomes of the project, from the end users' point of view and experience. After all, the SatisFactory project concept puts the users in the centre of the development, the evaluation of performance and the acceptance.

Following the integration of the different components and toolkits and the installations at the industrial lab and the pilot sites, the SatisFactory framework performance is going to be evaluated along with its ability to offer a satisfying working environment. In order to do that, several tools have been developed for data collection and special focus is put on the evaluation of end users acceptance, addressing also the User Centred Design (UCD) methodological framework of the project.

The evaluation approach is based on a combination of indicators assessing Satisfaction, Business facilitation and Ease of use. Data will be collected after the initial and final implementation at all shop floors from the workers and the decision makers.

2. SATISFACTORY EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE EVALUATION

The SatisFactory evaluation framework is to provide the methodology to evaluate the fulfilment of the project objectives with respect to the user (workers and decision makers) requirements. Therefore, the scope of the evaluation process is to assess the fulfilment of the project objectives and the interoperation between the components of SatisFactory platform and the different stakeholders. In order to do that, the evaluation process requires the establishment of a series of evaluation scenarios and tests to be performed. The user-centred design approach is extended also here, using an iterative process, as it has been adopted throughout the project. Following the UCD concept, the evaluation is running in parallel with all design and integration activities and it involves the initial adaptation of the proposed framework into real-time conditions, its operation in the pilots, along with an extended period of evaluation.

It is noted that the definition of the framework for the evaluation of factory workers and decision makers' appreciation starts from the **project objectives**:

- 1 Context-aware control and re-adaptation of shop floor production facilities for increased productivity and flexibility in use of shop floor resources
- 2 Improvement of attractiveness and productivity through collaboration, social interaction and gamification approaches
- 3 Real-time knowledge-sharing and AR-based collaboration and training services
- 4 Improved shop floor feedback and decision making for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort
- 5 Adaptive and augmented interfaces for collaboration, knowledge sharing and real time support

As it has been discussed the solution will be deployed and evaluated in an Industrial Lab pilot and in large-scale Industrial Facilities from the Automotive and Energy factory domain (6th project objective).

However, it is necessary to determine a set of objectives, which are related to the end-user perspective, the **evaluation objectives**. The project objectives need to be translated into a set of end-user expectations and requirements that constitute the basis for the evaluation methodology. The fulfilment of these objectives will be evaluated through the various BSCs, which are defined in D1.2, which in turn has capitalised from D1.1. Moreover, the D2.1 has served as a basis for the components to be evaluated. The evaluation objectives identified are:

1. Performance improvement
2. Real-time knowledge-sharing
3. AR assisted operation and training
4. Collaborative working environment
5. Ease of use and overall satisfaction

Figure 1 Evaluation Objectives

Performance Improvement refers to the way end-users perform their jobs and the outcome of their work. SatisFactory will provide the ability to monitor the actions of the operator within the shop floor, verifying their correctness according to the knowledge base already acquired and, then, on the one hand, guiding the worker, on the other hand, reporting any deviation or irregularity in order to keep the optimum balance between worker satisfaction and performance. Thus, the evaluation of the latter aspect will make use of KPIs that aim to evaluate the outcome of the worker’s daily activities, taking into consideration the introduction of new technologies and tools, such as AR devices, sensors, cameras and so forth.

Real-time knowledge sharing includes many things in an operating environment. A worker requires a set of information, resources, data and guidelines, in order to successfully and timely complete a task. A supervisor or manager needs to have an overview of the available resources (equipment, personnel, time etc.), the priorities from the production department, the status of equipment and more, in order to organise the busy factory hive. To this end, the objective is to evaluate how SatisFactory facilitates knowledge sharing and timely response to the continuously changing conditions at the shop floor.

The factories of the future are going to be managed and operated by the managers and workers of the future. The term “collaboration” embraces many different aspects within an operating environment such as knowledge sharing, interaction, and gamification. A **Collaborative Working environment** is more attractive, facilitates social interaction, promotes the use of new technologies and improved industrial manufacturing methods, and

offers decision support for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort. In this context, we refer to the *Collaborative Working environment* in order to evaluate the novelty of the solutions proposed and, in particular, the level of appreciation of the innovative features which are introduced by SatisFactory.

AR assisted operation and training is one of the cutting-edge solutions presented within SatisFactory. In an operating mode, a certain Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) can be presented to the worker in an augmented reality environment, empowering him/her with the possibility to be more efficient, safer and to improve memorisation without interrupting the operation at the shop floor. The tools developed offer a real on-the-job training and assist operation in real-time. The training platform aims to leverage the intuitiveness of AR to deliver “on-the-job” training and education for both entry and senior-level workers.

Ease of use and overall satisfaction from the end users’ point of view, are necessary for the acceptance of new technologies and devices within the shop floor. Easy-to-use devices facilitate the workers to perceive the added value introduced by the adoption of such devices in relation with the level of knowledge and skills required to use them. Moreover, the importance of overall satisfaction in the workplace needs to be emphasised, so that the degree of fulfilment of every user expectation is taken into consideration.

The relation of the project objectives to the evaluation objective is clear and straightforward. It should be noted that for the evaluation of the project objectives, certain KPIs have been set out in the DoW for the 3 years of the project duration. The results for the first year have been analysed within D8.2.

For the measurement of the fulfilment of the evaluation objectives, a set of evaluation scenarios and test are presented in this deliverable, based on the methodology and criteria analysed in the next sections.

2.2 EVALUATION METHODOLOGY AND CRITERIA

The evaluation methodology of the SatisFactory framework depicts the user-centric approach that is in the core of this project. The worker involvement and satisfaction need to be carefully evaluated and improved, because the adoption of new technologies and tools is often delayed or even hindered by the workers refusal to integrate them to their daily activities. Two main methodologies have been combined; the user-centric approach and the ECOGRAI method.

2.2.1 Human-centric Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation within SatisFactory follows the human-centered design approach according to the ISO 9241-210 Standard 210 (ISO 2010). This was introduced in SatisFactory Deliverable D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines and will be shortly summarized here as introduction to the evaluation methodology.

The main characteristic is the iterative approach, i.e. we apply a continuous circle of gaining domain knowledge, deriving requirements, producing design solutions and evaluating

whether these solutions meet the requirements. This leads to new knowledge, which requests for creating new requirements or revising existing ones etc. The requirements are managed with the JIRA tool, which allows for creating a network of interrelated design artefacts in the interest of achieving design traceability as advocated by ISO 9241, see also (Ramesch and Jarke 2001).

2.2.1.1 Evaluation Approaches for First Iterations

During the first iterations, the used methods focus on evaluating whether the developed solutions are effective and efficient for completing the envisaged tasks. Besides assessing the solutions, in this period optimizing them is also possible, so the methodologies also try to result in suggestions for improving the former iterations. For this, we consider the following methods appropriate.

2.2.1.1.1 Focus Groups

A focus group is a group of end users or other experts for a system under examination. The focus group discusses given designs and can also revise the designs during the focus group session. However, the examined design must have been designed by somebody else. A moderator makes sure that the group stays on topic and that everyone contributes to the discussion.

Main purpose of a focus group session is to test a product idea. Mental models, personal preferences, reluctances and wishes shall be identified. In addition, focus groups can be used in order to validate user requirements.

The focus group shall be as homogeneous as possible. I.e. the boss should not participate in the same focus group as the secretary does. The ideal number of participants is 7.

2.2.1.1.2 Field Studies

The actual product is tested by potential end users. Depending on the state of the product, the field study can be conducted with a prototype in a lab environment or with a more mature product deployed in a productive environment.

The users perform typical test task with the product. The test person asks the users to think aloud, i.e. to verbalize every thought during task execution. The test person is foremost an observer and does not explain anything about the project but tries to find out how much the users can achieve with the product without explanation. However, the test person can ask the users questions if rationale or uncertainties in some of the users' actions cannot be observed. And, of course, quiet participants need gentle reminders to continue thinking aloud.

In this sense, for every critical situation of use, it is tested, whether this situation is a problem according to ISO 9241-110 (ISO 2006). Thinking aloud helps to identify reasons.

The results are documented during and after the session. If several user groups exist, testing with 5 users per group detect the majority of critical situations.

2.2.1.1.3 Expert Evaluations

Besides letting the evaluation be performed by users, there are also methods which can be performed by experts. This is especially useful if it is for some reason difficult to let users participate.

One expert evaluation is the inspection on basis of user requirements. For this, an expert tests whether the product does what it should do. The user requirements, which were developed in scope of the user context, are the test criteria. The overall system assessment is the sum of degrees of fulfilment of every user requirement. Target is the optimization of a system by extension of the possible effectively executable tasks.

During a scenario-based walkthrough, 2 experts execute typical tasks using the system. For every critical situation of use, it is tested, whether this situation is a problem according to ISO 9241-110 (ISO 2006). So, this approach is like a field study with the difference that it is conducted by experts instead of end users.

2.2.1.1.4 Heuristic Evaluation

Separated from each other, several usability experts evaluate a system by 10 heuristics. On average 5 experts are able to detect 75% of all usability issues. This is a cheap and effective method to detect the majority of issues, developed by (Nielsen 1994). It can also be conducted in an early stage of development. However, it cannot completely replace user tests as it will not identify all issues.

The heuristic evaluation is conducted in 4 phases. In the preparation phase, the experts familiarize themselves with the product. Then, the actual evaluation is conducted according to the heuristics by 3-5 experts, optimally 2 runs, and 1-2 hours each. Each identified issue is assessed and documented according to its severity on a 5-point scale, taking into account its frequency, impact and persistency. In the results phase, the experts sit together in order to group problems according to the ratings. In the final solution finding phase, the experts brainstorm together with the developers.

The 10 heuristics are:

1. The system should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.
2. The system should speak the user's language, with words, phrases and concepts familiar to the user, rather than system-oriented terms. Follow real-world conventions, making information appear in a natural and logical order.
3. Users often choose system functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.
4. Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing. Follow platform conventions.
5. Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.
6. Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the dialogue to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.
7. Accelerators—unseen by the novice user—may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the system can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.
8. Dialogues should not contain information which is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.
9. Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.
10. Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.

2.2.1.2 Final Evaluation Approaches

The evaluation of final implementations is checking for overall usability and user experience and whether the general ergonomic principles according to ISO 9241-110 are met (ISO 2006). Of course, at this point in time, solutions cannot be optimized anymore, so the methodologies are only focussing on assessing but not on optimizing. The main method for final evaluations is a field study with the deployed product (cf. Section 2.2.1.1.2).

Alternatively, the questionnaires introduced in this Section can be used. All questionnaires are listed in Annexe I.

2.2.1.2.1 SUS – System Usability Scale

The System Usability Scale (Brooke 1996) measures level of required help, level of required introduction and complexity of a system. It is a commonly used method for computing subjective usability assessment of participants to a single number. The SUS is very lightweight since only 10 questions need to be answered by participants.

(Sauro 2011) collected data from over 5000 users across over 500 system usability scale evaluations. He compiled them to a benchmark to which an own SUS value can be compared.

2.2.1.2.2 AttrakDiff

AttrakDiff captures the users' perception of a product. A free-to-use online tool is provided at <http://attrakdiff.de/>. Users are presented 28 pairs of opposite adjectives and are asked to assign these to the product under examination using a 7-point scale. Different adjective-pairs are then grouped and evaluated to the dimensions as follows (Hassenzahl 2003).

- Pragmatic Quality (PQ):
Indicates how successful users are in achieving their goals using the product.
- Hedonic Quality - Stimulation (HQ-S):
Mankind has an inherent need to develop and move forward. This dimension indicates to what extent the product can support those needs in terms of novel, interesting and stimulating functions, contents and interaction- and presentation-styles.
- Hedonic Quality (HQ-I):
Indicates to what extent the product allows users to identify with it.
- Attractiveness (ATT):
A global value that is based on the other dimensions. Hedonic and pragmatic qualities are independent of one another and contribute equally to the rating of attractiveness (Hassenzahl 2001).

2.2.1.2.3 User Experience Questionnaire

UEQ – the user experience questionnaire – is similar to AttrakDiff in the sense that users must assign a product on a 7-point scale to 26 pairs of opposite adjectives. Most of the UEQ adjectives are different to those used by AttrakDiff. UEQ calculates scores for the following categories (Rauschenberger 2013).

- Attractiveness:
General impression towards the product. Do users like or dislike the product? This scale is a pure valence dimension.
- Efficiency:
Is it possible to use the product fast and efficiently? Does the user interface look organized?
- Perspicuity:
Is it easy to understand how to use the product? Is it easy to get familiar with the product?
- Dependability:
Does the user feel in control of the interaction? Is the interaction with the product confident and predictable?
- Stimulation:
Is it interesting and exciting to use the product? Does the user feel motivated to further use the product?
- Novelty:
Is the design of the product innovative and creative? Does the product grab users' attention?

2.2.2 ECOGRAI Evaluation Methodology

ECOGRAI is a method originally introduced to design and to implement Performance Indicator Systems (PIS) for industrial organizations and used by the decision makers of the Production Management Systems (PMS) to measure the achievement of their objectives (Doumeingts *et al.*, 1995).

The approach involves two stages:

- a) Top-down approach for the logical process of analysis, decomposing the objectives of the strategic levels into objectives for operational levels. For SatisFactory this is depicted in the selection on the areas that the management and supervisor levels wish to focus in terms of assessing the technologies and tools through the project.
- b) Bottom-up approach for the concrete process of participative implementation. Forming the conditions that allow to support the dialogue between the different company levels allows the identification of indicators that are acceptable by and make sense to the future users of the products.

The six steps of the ECOGRAI method are depicted below.

Figure 2 The six steps of the ECOGRAI method

Application of ECOGRAI to the SatisFactory project

The ECOGRAI methodology will be capitalised within SatisFactory for the selection of the KPIs to be investigated in order to evaluate the fulfilment of the project objectives and the value of its results at the workers' and at the decision makers' levels. A detailed analysis will be based on this methodology, taking also advantage of the existing evaluation framework and KPIs already existing in the shop floors. Certain phases are split into sub-phases for ease of the implementation (Lobna *et al.*, 2013).

2.2.2.1 Phase 0: Modelling of the Production System Control Structure and Identification of the PCC

Phase 0.1 Modelling of the Production System Control Structure

The shop floors involved in SatisFactory have an already defined structure of their production system. However, this structure should be revisited with a critical eye, in order to help define the decision centres, their activities, their links, as well as the objectives and the drivers. The structure can be depicted using the existing management tools and/or the GRAI Grid, distinguishing the strategic, tactical and operational levels. It should be also noted that the hierarchical and functional approaches are also considered.

Phase 0.2 Identification of the PCC

The PCC are, in fact, the decision centres, which have a principal influence on the system control as a consequence of their activities. They are traditionally available at the strategic level, but not necessarily at the tactical and operational levels. The end users will identify the set of PCC that covers the various functions (engineering, manufacturing, quality and maintenance) of all grids and at various decision levels.

In order to identify a PCC, the GRAI grid must be considered, in the form of a matrix with a horizontal production axis and a vertical managerial axis. On the managerial or control axis the various decision levels in the Production System are presented, usually as strategic, tactical and operational levels. This categorisation is kept here, taking into consideration the management, supervisor and worker levels. On the production axis the activities required to carry out the complete manufacturing procedure within the SatisFactory shop floors are included (such as design, manufacture, maintenance, quality, delivery, recycling).

A decision centre is defined by a function and decision level cross. From these decision centres the Principal Control Centres are selected and defined, as those having the most influence on the system control, because of the activities taking place within them.

2.2.2.2 Phase 1: Identification of the PCC Objectives and Coherence Analysis

Phase 1.1: Identification of the PCC Objectives

The objectives usually come from the Business Plan of the infrastructure. In the SatisFactory shop floors they are primarily based in terms of optimisation of the triplet Quality / Cost / Customer Satisfaction, with the Lead Time being incorporated into the Cost and Customer Satisfaction aspect. However, the triplet becomes a rectangular within this project, bringing up front the importance of Worker Satisfaction.

Phase 1.2 and 1.3: Identification of the Global and PCC Objectives for each function and Coherence Analysis

The global or overall objectives and the objectives of each function need to be aligned. The main issue at this step of the analysis is to make sure that the existing links between the global/overall objectives of the various functions are well identified in order to make sure that there are no perverse effects. In the case of such an effect, the objectives assigned to a function might prevent another function to achieve its objectives.

2.2.2.3 Phase 2: Identification of the PCC Drivers and analysis of the conflicts

The Drivers are the one of the most important parts of the procedure, which is usually overlooked. They must be defined, taking into account that they have intra-function and inter-function influences. For each PCC, the aim here is to evaluate the relationships with the Drivers, the degree, the origin of the influence and whether the Driver has a direct or indirect effect on the considered objective.

2.2.2.4 Phase 3: Identification of the PCC PIs and Internal Coherence Analysis

Phase 3.1: Identification of the PIs for the PCCs

At this step, the methodology moves on with the identification of Performance Indicators for each PCC. The approach uses the knowledge of all the people involved in the study and this identification is validated by an internal coherence analysis inside each Principal Control Centre. However, this detailed analysis can result to a great number of PIs, in order to cover all aspects of the performed tasks within a PCC. It is imperative to associate the PIs with the objectives and to select the few that will form the set of Key Performance Indicators, the KPIs.

Phase 3.2: Internal Coherence Analysis of the PCC

The Objectives, the Drivers and the Performance Indicators need to be consistent for each PCC. Cyclic diagrams or coherence panels can be built to allow for the identification of links between the elements of the PCC, as well as the weight of their contribution. The latter is complimenting the effort within Phase 3.1, in order to end up with a set of KPIs, rather than with an extensive list of PIs.

2.2.2.5 Phase 4: Design of the PI Information System

An indicator is a means to measure a certain activity. There are three aspects that need to be considered: a) which data is necessary and b) how will they be processed, in order to generate the values of the indicators, c) what are the target values or at least an acceptable operating level. Certain PIs exist already in the shop floors, but they mainly address the technical part of the implementation and the influence on the final product/service. Within T5.2, focus is also given into the evaluation of the overall solution, so, when necessary, the partners can use a specification sheet for each indicator which breaks down the PI and makes it more understandable and reusable.

ECOGRAI Study	Phase 4: Indicator Specification	Function: Decision Centre: Period:
<p><i>Indicator</i></p> <p><i>Objectives</i></p> <p><i>Drivers</i></p> <p><i>Basic Information</i></p> <p><i>Origin</i></p> <p><i>Processing</i></p> <p><i>Required evolution</i></p> <p><i>Possible perverse effects and possible influence on other indicators</i></p> <p><i>Actions to make the indicator evolve in the required direction</i></p> <p><i>Description and demonstration (e.g representation using graphics)</i></p>		

Table 1 Specification Sheet for PI of the ECOGRAI method

It is noted that the Specification Sheet is an extensive tool that might not be fully capitalised within the duration of the SatisFactory project, as iterations and reworks show more complete results after consecutive implementations. It is much more easy to use PIs already defined and used by the end users. However, the basic aspects can be considered, in order to select the most representative KPIs.

2.2.2.6 Phase 5: Integration of the Performance Indicator information system in the Production information system

This phase is optional and it can be supported by the use of an EIS (Executive Information System) tool. In case of existing data bases it is an option that can be applied or it can be

revisited once they will be in use. Moreover, existing information systems supporting specific functions or operations (such as the CMMS for the Maintenance operation) can be considered. They are valuable not only for the generation of PIs in the previous phases of the analysis, but also in the integration phase, as they are part of the Production information system.

2.2.3 Combined Evaluation Methodology

The two methodologies described in the previous sections are complimentary, as they address the evaluation issue from different points of view, considering the human factor, as well as the system for the availability and sharing of information and influences within an industrial environment. The combined evaluation methodology allows for the usage of tools from both approaches that are suitable for each shop floor. The methodology is translated into the evaluation criteria described in the following section.

Moreover, considering both methodologies, a set of Criteria and respective Evaluation Tests has been set out, taking into account the human-centred design approach, the principle control centres and decision variables definition, under the umbrella of the heuristic evaluation concept.

2.2.4 Evaluation Criteria

The following criteria represent a means of measure established to assess the degree to which SatisFactory solutions are able to meet the objectives. For this purpose, the combined evaluation methodology described in the previous sections is translated into five criteria:

- Usability
- Knowledge integration
- Perception of working experience
- User acceptance
- Impact of SatisFactory

Such criteria are translated into KPIs, which can be furtherly grouped into three main groups, such as *Satisfaction Indicators*, *Business Facilitation Indicators*, and *Ease of Use Indicators* (Section 2.2.5). More details will be given in the next sections.

2.2.4.1 Usability

Usability is one of the most widely used tools for assessing the perceived usability of a product by a user. It is a broad term that incorporates better graphical representation of simulation input and output, simple navigation and flexible control, as well as suitability for the respective address use. Appropriately combining and visualising all types and levels of information involved in industrial manufacturing processes is undoubtedly a heavily complex task.

To do so, SatisFactory has to support a series of visualisation, incident management and decision support components and techniques appropriate for the process operators and supervisors. Within our project, the design and exploitation of user-centric technologies represent the main aspect of this work. Hence, the usability criterion aims to evaluate the

suitability and the effect on the shop floor, shifting the focus on the user work experience rather than on the product. Moreover, the technologies and tools introduced will be assessed in terms of level of learnability and applicability.

2.2.4.2 Knowledge Integration

The information that flows within the shop floor is immense. Real-time data from the sensorial system, manuals, standard operating procedures, emergency operating procedures, standard guidelines, customised requirements and specification and so on represent the variety both size and type. This immense knowledge needs to be integrated and filtered, in order to provide to each worker what is necessary, when it is necessary.

With Knowledge Integration we want to assess how the information is integrated through the implementation of semantic models. Such models put the foundations for a semantically enriched environment where the shop floor knowledge is gathered, processed and shared. Moreover, Knowledge Integration refers to the evaluation of the exploitation of the shop floor knowledge, in the way that the shop floor activities are supported or that this knowledge is translated, managed, and then exposed through the SatisFactory platform. It is also noted that the developed framework will deliver different views of information depending on the organisational level and localisation of the end-users, which is also a parameter to be considered in the evaluation.

2.2.4.3 Perception of working experience

The purpose of this criterion is to gain feedback from workers and decision makers about the value of their work experience. Social and environmental aspects of the end-user working experience will be investigated in order to obtain the workers' point of view. Among the aspects to be evaluated from the end-user, it's worth mentioning: work organisation, attitude of the other workers, ergonomics, safety, quality of training and assistance. The perception of the user's working experience is about motivations, attitudes, expectations, behavioural patterns, and constraints. It is about the types of interactions people have, how they feel about an experience, and what actions they expect to take (Pavliscak, 2014).

The introduction of gamification and collaboration tools, the use of AR-based devices change the work environment and certainly influence the perception of the working experience. For example, the revolution of the training environment through the introduction of AR devices and semantic technologies is a relevant aspect of this evaluation criterion. In this context, the development of an on-job training platform requires the assessment of the training outcomes from the user point of view. This may include the evaluation of many aspects, such as, the effectiveness of the training methods and materials used; the relevance of the training content; the knowledge, attitudes and skills gained by the trainees.

2.2.4.4 User acceptance

The user acceptance is defined as the willingness within a user group (workers or decision makers) to employ new technologies for the tasks they are designed to support. Thus, such concept is not being applied to situations in which users claim they will employ it without providing evidence of use, or to the use of a technology for purposes unintended by the designers or procurers. From the evaluation point of view the end point is to verify that the solution provided works for the user. Therefore, the user acceptance criterion has been

defined in order to create reasonable metrics for evaluating the acceptance of the technologies introduced by SatisFactory within the industrial partners' shop floor.

It is stressed that the user acceptance will not be evaluated only within the scope and the duration of the project, but also as the willingness of the involved stakeholders to embrace and reuse the developed tools in their everyday activities. The extension of the use of SatisFactory tools to more processes and operations after the project duration is what we consider an interesting potential.

2.2.4.5 Impact of SatisFactory

This criterion aims to assess the overall impact of SatisFactory within the specific pilot sites, and then, in the aspects that span across the 5 objectives from a more general perspective. Different aspects of the SatisFactory impact, e.g. Economic, Management, Design and the like, will become a common base for a set of performance indicators. From the satisfaction point of view, the reduction of time for operations and frequency of system's failures might be two meaningful aspects to evaluate. Instead, from the business facilitation point of view, financial aspects such as cost of installation and maintenance or ROI can be also meaningful toward the definition of a set of KPIs for this general purpose criterion.

In the Impact of SatisFactory criterion we aim to assess the overall feeling and added value that the framework leaves to the end users. In a sense we wish to evaluate how much of a change, impact the tools and components, as well as the entire framework have on the daily activities and the satisfaction and well-being of the workers. A considerable impact will facilitate adoption and extension of usage.

2.2.5 Performance Indicators

In this section the performance indicators to be used are presented, according to the criteria and categories discussed in the previous sections.

2.2.5.1 Usability

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Usability	Satisfaction Indicators	
	U1	Effectiveness of tasks completed using the SatisFactory framework
	U2	Percentage of reduction of time on a single task
	U3	Percentage of reduction of failures
	U4	Percentage of correct identification of incidents at the shop floor
	U5	Number of operators using the suggestion platform
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	U6	Percentage of successful re-adaptation and appropriate work assignment to actors
	U7	Number of identified areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks
	U8	Provision of straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status
	Ease of Use Indicators	
U9	Variety of visualisations offered	
U10	Percentage of workers feeling motivated and playful	
U11	Facilitation of task performance	

2.2.5.2 Knowledge Integration

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Knowledge Integration	Satisfaction Indicators	
	KI1	Percentage of appropriate/suitable data/information received
	KI2	Percentage of on time delivery of data/information
	KI3	Reduced average time for completion of training procedures
	KI4	Number of submitted suggestions

	KI5	Number of collaboration actions through the platform
	KI6	Identification of patterns of workers' movement at the shop floor
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	KI7	Reduction of errors related to accurate localisation of information and/or objects in the shop floor
	KI8	Number of accepted suggestions
	KI9	Reduction of time for training procedures preparation
	KI10	Training cost reduction
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	KI11	Percentage of availability of efficient information through AR tools
	KI12	Percentage of provision of unreadable and incomprehensible data/information

2.2.5.3 Perception of working experience

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Working Experience	Satisfaction Indicators	
	WE1	Percentage of demonstration of safety procedures and ergonomics through the platform
	WE2	Usefulness/Improvement of training sessions for knowledge and skills enrichment
	WE3	Percentage of workers that used the AR components
	WE4	Percentage of workers that would reuse the AR components
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	WE5	Continuous automatic monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras
	WE6	Increase of safety at work due to usage of SatisFactory tools
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	WE7	Reduction in the number of requests for help to other workers/experts
	WE8	Provision of complete and reliable training
	WE9	Reduction of work-related stress

2.2.5.4 User acceptance

Criterion	ID	Indicator
User Acceptance	Satisfaction Indicators	
	UA1	Level of user engagement
	UA2	Level of applicability of lessons learned to everyday activities
	UA3	Percentage of successful access to data/information through AR platform
	UA4	Level of engagement of operators using the suggestion platform (>3 suggestions per year)
	UA5	Level of engagement of operators using the collaboration platform (>3 collaborations per year)
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	UA6	Reduction of process or machine downtime
	UA7	Number of SOP transformed into AR tools
	UA8	Level of improved sense of team spirit
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	UA9	Reduction of misinterpretations
UA10	Increased attractiveness using gamification tools	
UA11	Percentage of workers feeling participating into a user community, having novel ways for social interaction and communication	
UA12	Percentage of positive feedbacks from operators	

2.2.5.5 Impact of SatisFactory

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Impact	Satisfaction Indicators	
	OI1	Incidents handled by the SF System
	OI2	Overall satisfaction regarding tool's features and functionality
	OI3	Frequency of the failures of the system
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	OI4	Cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance
	OI5	Return on Investment (ROI)

	OI6	Criticality of the failures of the system
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	OI7	Level of applicability of SatisFactory tools
	OI8	Fit for purpose (the tool is fulfilling the expressed needs and it fits for the purpose it was developed)
	OI9	Level of overall aesthetic attractiveness to the end users

3. SATISFACTORY PILOT SITES (AREA ANALYSIS AND DESIGN)

3.1 CERTH/CPERI

3.1.1 Description of selected pilot areas

CERTH/CPERI has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). Also Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software, with OPC connectivity. CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485). Within the project, CERTH/CPERI will utilize its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI's process plants where the Industrial Lab cases will take place. Also CERTH/CPERI's selected shop-floor processes will be used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions. CERTH/CPERI's infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

CERTH/CPERI shop floor view (1)

CERTH/CPERI shop floor view (2)

Figure 3 CERTH/CPERI shop floor view

Pilot plants produce each day real-time data stored in repositories that provide a significant amount of information currently analysed using conventional tools while the decision making

relies on information which is compiled in a manual manner by the process operators and the process supervisors. Besides the collection, analysis and deployment of automated actions, the aforementioned infrastructure is equipped with data visualization tools combined with content aware functions using diagnosis and alarm triggering tools. The user interacts with the devices, the sensors and the actuators through a set of user-friendly human machine interfaces (HMI) that provide the basis for the decision making process in real-time. Furthermore, the data can be accessed by local or remote information points and can be managed by supervisory functions. Thus, the operators can intuitively understand the status and the various conditions of the process equipment and respond accordingly upon demand. The aforementioned infrastructure is developed using a set of adaptive user interfaces combined with flexible sensor topologies that are able to tackle the heterogeneity of the various devices which are present in a smart factory.

3.1.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

One of the main operational constraints of CERTH/CPERI is related to safety, material handling and timely performance of operational procedures. All the processes on the shop floor include chemical and other sensitive materials which require special handling regarding safety. In order to avoid incidents or accidents, the safety measures are very specific and strict (according to ISO standards, e.g. 9001) and all workers must be cautious and follow the procedures carefully. Also the material handling defines a set of constraints related to the treatment of specific substances (chemicals in liquid, gas or solid state) during the preparation or the operation of the process units.

Besides the internal operational constraints related to the procedures performed at the process units, there are a set of constraints related to the relationship and the sharing of information with the clients. This means that any data that has been categorized as confidential is not allowed to be distributed outside of the internal ICT infrastructures of CERTH/CPERI and provided to third parties. This information is about technical schematics, instrumentation diagrams, process documents, financial data, new developments, customer details, reference bill of materials (process and electrical BOMs), production plans etc.

Regarding legal constraints, all workers of CERTH/CPERI sign a confidentiality agreement regarding the procedures, the infrastructure and the data (experimental or theoretical) that are produced from the plant floor procedures and plant operation. The produced data (raw signals from the field or processed data) are to be handled as need to know basis and are distributed according to the respective contracts as signed per customer. The analytical data are covered by the confidentiality and quality assurance procedures described by the respective ISO (9001 or 17025).

3.2 SUNLIGHT

3.2.1 Description of selected pilot areas

Sunlight has several production lines, applying different manufacturing processes in each production stage. Two of them have been selected to be the pilot areas in which the

SatisFactory components will be installed and tested. The first one is the battery cell formation process (jar formation), which is the last stage of the PzS batteries production line and the second one is Motive power (traction) batteries assembly line.

- **Jar Formation pilot area**

The initial formation charge of a lead-acid battery, whether in the form of plates or as an already assembled battery, is quite a complex bundle of chemical reactions. It is important to know in principle about the most important parameters controlling this process in order to achieve good reproducible results with reasonable efforts.

Jar formation is applied to already assembled battery cells. In the Jar formation area there are Battery formation modules which are circulating the electrolyte through each battery cell. The formation process for the battery cells begins with the filling process. The battery cells are connected to the battery formation modules which are responsible to fill and circulate the electrolyte in to the cells and the battery charger which are performing the formation process. The time gap between electrolyte filling and the initiation of the formation process is critical. If the formation starts immediately after filling, a significant amount of acid may remain unreacted. There are several formation algorithms and profiles that can be applied. Several conditions must be considered for applying the most proper formation profile.

Figure 4 Battery formation modules with Acid circulation

- **Motive power (Traction) battery assembly**

Sunlight Motive power batteries can cover all types of motive power needs, from light duty single-shift operation to heavy duty multi-shift operations, and are suitable for all industrial electric forklift types, such as counterbalanced, narrow aisle and hand trucks. The Motive Power battery assembly line is a manual assembly line.

The Motive Power battery assembly procedure includes the following stages:

- Cells fitting into metal tray
- Inspection level electrolyte
- Battery cleaning
- Connectors fitting

- Inspection bolts and voltage
- Labels fitting
- Advisories & appurtenances fitting
- Palletizing & packing with nylon

Figure 5 Sunlight Motive Power Battery

Figure 6 Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line

3.2.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

The operational constraints that are applied in Sunlight concern not only the production itself but also the relationship with the customers and between employees. One of the main principle at Sunlight is the strict adhering to all health and safety as well as environmental regulations for all production lines, including the selected as pilot areas. For this reason there are important rules which are mandatory for all employees and apply to the entire territory of the plant and production areas. Concerning the quality, there are also particular constrains that are applied to each production stage. All these operations are performed according to the international standards (ISO 9001, ISO 14001, BS OHSAS 18001) that are already installed in Sunlight.

Legal constrains are enforced to the employees related with the confidential information that they handle in each case. This means that any data that has been categorized as confidential is not allowed to be exported from the company and provided to third parties. This information can be technical documents, financial data, new developments, client lists and details, reference lists, production plans etc.

3.3 COMAU

3.3.1 Description of selected pilot areas

COMAU is a global supplier of industrial automation systems for the automotive manufacturing sector and a global provider of full maintenance services. To the “automotive” Customers worldwide, COMAU offers its capacity as “System Integrator” and its complete engineering solutions, from product development to the realization of industrial process automation systems. COMAU provides also integrated services to the manufacturing plants, from assistance to the production start-up phases, up to equipment and plant full maintenance activities. COMAU comprises the following organizational units: Body Assembly, Powertrain Systems, Robotics & Service, Adaptive Solutions. The continuous improvement of products, processes and services, through the application of the most advanced innovative technological solutions, allows COMAU to contribute to its Customers’ competitive advantage. Research and development activities are aimed primarily at the evolution of technologies applied to manufacturing systems, but also to the creation of a company portfolio in terms of standardised product/process solutions, in order to improve the overall competitiveness of the production of the company’s affiliates.

Within the SatisFactory Project mainly two of the organizational units are involved: Robotics and Body Assembly.

- **Robotics: robot wrist assembly**

In the robotics business unit the robot assembly is an operation performed completely by hand. The robot arm is composed by several main sub-components (i.e. base, forearm, arm, wrist), each of them is assembled in a specific “Operating Station”.

Each station is equipped with a specific set of tools, power-tools and parts that allows the operator to perform the assembly operations, working in the best conditions in terms of movements, lighting, components reach, etc. in other words from the ergonomic point of view.

Within the SatisFactory Project, the most representative assembly phase analyzed is the wrist assembly. This operation is critical because for different robot families, the internal components are similar, but with little variations, that mean different assembly procedures. The operators are usually dedicated to specific sub-assembly operations, thus they know very well the right sequence of operations, but sometimes they are requested to move in different places in order to replace colleagues or to face different products demands. Under these particular conditions, the operators’ workload is significantly increased because they need to readapt to a different production process.

In this case, a system able to support the operator with a step-by-step interactive manual could significantly reduce the risk of errors in the assembly procedures, while reducing the mental workload of the operator and improving the overall efficiency. Moreover, the introduction of digital tools like calipers, dynamometers, torque wrenches etc. will allow the system to produce automated checklists that certify also the quality of the product. This is actually done manually by means of modules filled by the operators.

Following in red is highlighted the component assembled in the reference Operating Station.

Figure 7 Robot wrist assembly

- **Body Assembly: remote maintenance on robotized production cell**

Body assembly lines are very complex systems constituted by robotic arms, mechanical tools controlled by means of compressed air and transport systems electro-actuated. When a fault occurs, the maintenance staff is called by the operators and has to fix it in the shortest timeframe in order to avoid costly production losses. The main problem is that maintenance staff cannot always fix the problem alone, sometimes an external intervention or support is required from engineering or from skilled personnel not always available. In this case a support platform including tools that allow remote maintenance and collaboration as well as augmented reality could significantly reduce the MTTR (Mean Time To Repair) of the machines, allowing considerable savings.

Within the SatisFactory project a robotized production cell will be used as test bed in order to develop and test the aforementioned features.

The main components constituting the COMAU SatisFactory Test Cell are respectively an APC (Accumulating Pallet Conveyor) feeding system, two robots devoted to handling and welding functionalities and a tool-table. Hereafter a short description for each component shown is provided:

1. APC: it is a production line feeding system in charge of collecting elements and sub-assemblies built in external lines or coming from metal stamping, with the final goal of providing a continuous and automated elements availability to the production line. A central chain ring allows the pallets movement. Each pallet hosts a single element and, once it is removed by the robot, a synchronized stopper movement allows the pallet to “turn down” and reach again the beginning of the conveyor in order to be

filled again, while the next pallet makes a step forward and it again ready to fill the line with a new element.

2. Handling Robot: this subsystem is composed by a robot equipped with a gripper that includes clamps, centering pins and it is designed to move elements from/to different stations, transport systems or external feeding systems
3. Welding Robot: also named “Spot Welding Machine”, is a subsystem composed by a specific robot equipped with a spot welding gun. It can be easily customized in order to weld in the more appropriate way each metal sheet thickness, starting from two 0,5mm to three 1,4 mm metal parts.
4. Tool-table with fixtures and lock-pins, with the main function of holding in position the elements to be welded. This provides the right geometry to the finished car part.

These embedded systems are representative examples of complex devices that compose typically production lines in car body assembly processes.

Figure 8 Body Assembly

3.3.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

Main legal constraints in COMAU are related to the confidentiality of some data like financial data, new developments, client lists and details, production plans etc., as well as specific phases of the production process as well as the technical documents of the components (in some cases protected by means of international patents).

A second important group of constraints from the legal point of view is related to the interaction with labour unions. In this case, the application of novel technologies in the industrial environment like cameras, indoor localization systems, etc. could lead to privacy issues, as well as ergonomics issues, like the application of glasses for augmented reality, that is actually not normed, and a constant usage could cause problems not yet classified.

From the operational point of view, main constraints are related from one side to the production itself, from the other, like for SunLight the wide number of international standards and norms that machines and products must respect, as well as the adherence to the World Class Manufacturing program pillars (shown in the following picture), where COMAU is putting significant effort in order to improve the complete process chain.

World Class Manufacturing Pillars

Figure 9 World Class Manufacturing program pillars

4. EVALUATION PROCESS

In this Section the approach for the scenarios used in the evaluation framework is analysed. In the next iteration the overall preparation process for the system evaluation in terms of performance and user experience will be completed, based on the exact Business Scenarios.

4.1 EVALUATION SCENARIOS (ES)

The evaluation of the SatisFactory components, key exploitable products and the overall framework takes into account the Business Scenarios that have been developed as a result of the efforts of T1.1 End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications, T1.2 Models for actors and procedures interconnection and T1.3 Use Cases and Scenarios. The BSCs are being continuously updated and improved and this is going to be depicted in the next iterations of D1.1 User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines and D1.2 Use Case analysis and application scenarios and descriptions.

In an attempt to simplify the evaluation procedure and in order for it to be valuable to other BSCs and processes which are not part of the SatisFactory analysis, the Evaluation Scenarios are perceived and designed to be usable during and after the duration of the project. They are tied to the BSCs in the sense that they are realised in them by grouping common KPIs, process steps, tools and applications used, tasks required to be implemented by the workers etc. They are also tied to the evaluation objectives and criteria as they derived from them, in attempt to evaluate the overall impact of the SatisFactory framework. As the BSCs will be revisited in the next iterations, so will the corresponding Evaluation Scenarios and the associated Evaluation Tests.

4.1.1 Evaluation Scenario ES1: Supporting Assembly Operations

The assembly operations have been identified as of critical importance, as they can be individual tasks or a set of steps in a broader task that workers need to undertake. They are common in automotive and heavy equipment industries, electronics, defence, aerospace, telecommunications, power & automation, energy & resource, naval engineering, as it has also been defined by AREA. The scope of this evaluation scenario is to support the workers in carrying out assembly operations by providing them the required information using real-time localisation, AE, DSS, information from the automation system and SOP, depending on the use case to be studied and implemented.

4.1.1.1 ES1.1 Automated support for assembly operations

In this evaluation scenario, the worker is prompt to perform assembly operations in a standardised way. The layout is relatively stable, in the sense that the working stations are set and the worker performs the steps in a defined manner. However, different products

require different set of materials and tools to be identified and selected, a series of manual movements to be conducted in a certain way, exact points to be sought and identified etc. A successful support automatically suggests the adaptation of the specific steps to be performed, feeds the information to the HR workbalance toolkit and provides the worker with the required information and visualisation tools to complete the task.

Addressed requirements

The main goal is to address the multiple challenges in the assembly operations and help the workers by facilitating the provision of information and resources to respond in time and effectively.

The evaluation process will consider the aspects required for the successful completion of an assembly task. The on time acknowledgment of the requirement to take up such a task comes first and then the assignment of the suitable worker in term of skills and availability follows. This procedure will result in a notification to a specific worker to carry out a specific task using a specific set of tools. Hence, a number of evaluation tests will be performed to assess among others the reduction of assembly faults while increasing ergonomics, convenience and worker satisfaction.

4.1.1.2 ES1.2 AR supported assembly operations

In the AR supported assembly operations evaluation scenario the worker is required to perform an assembly operation using an AR SOP Presentation Tool. The main issue lies in the aspect of customised customer requirements and the need to pay special attention to certain steps of the procedure for safety reasons. Although the actual assembly is done using up to a certain degree an automated system, attention needs to be given to the ergonomics and safety features also.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of this scenario is to address the automatic assembly operations, so as to enable efficient and error-free task fulfilment since the aspect of customisation which emerges quite often increases the difficulty of carrying out the steps required.

The main perspective in the evaluation scenario is to address user satisfaction related to the performance of the provided tools (localisation, AR, recommendations given, assignments made etc.). Thus, a number of evaluation tests will be performed taking also into account knowledge sharing, provision of valuable feedback on effective operations. To this end, the support in the decision making concerning the effective workload, resources management and with visual tools will also be evaluated.

4.1.2 Evaluation Scenario ES2: Offering Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing Services

The scope is to evaluate the services offered related to maintenance (corrective and preventive), re-adaptation and HR workload balancing through the SatisFactory framework. These services are required for the efficient operation at the shop floor, to ensure that the equipment is up and running in order to fulfil production needs, to ensure the safety of the workers at the shop floor level, to reduce the work related stress and to efficiently manage human resources.

4.1.2.1 ES2.1 Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing

In this evaluation scenario, a failure in equipment occurs and the incident is detected, the work allocation is suggested as well as the re-adaptation of the scheduling. Moreover, the worker prompted to respond to take action is provided with the set of tools and information required to perform the task and he/she is able to collaborate with others who have taken care of similar work orders and to take advantage of their experiences.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation scenario is to address malfunctions and failures in a well-defined and more automated way. All involved stakeholders at different operational level can view information about the occurring incident and the workers at the shop floor are guided with the appropriate set of tools and information to address the task.

A malfunction detected by the automation system occurs and it reaches the iDSS through the Middleware. iDSS evaluates the input and suggests a course of actions, as well as the necessary resources for it. Therefore, the evaluation scenario addresses user satisfaction in timely and suitable notification, the timely mitigation actions suggested, the quality of the provided tools and guidelines etc. A number of evaluation tests are going to be performed according to the description in Annex IV.

4.1.2.2 ES2.2 Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing

In this evaluation scenario a preventive maintenance program has been scheduled and it is in turn to be realised. The prioritisation of activities is important, as well as the work scheduling, allowing for the complete preventive maintenance action to take place. The work allocation is suggested based on available resources taking into consideration that re-adaptation may be needed. The worker assigned to perform the task is provided with the tools and information required and is also informed on the SOP to be followed.

Addressed requirements

The main goal is to address the preventive maintenance actions, required to ensure that the shop floors are up and running. Apart from the details related to the exact BSCs, operating using preventive maintenance as a main activity has a positive effect also on the sense of safety and satisfaction of the workers.

A preventive maintenance action needs to be implemented, according to the schedules and plans of the Production and Maintenance departments. The planned aspect of the action may allow for scheduling flexibility, which is considered by the re-adaptation and HR workload management toolkit. Moreover, this flexibility, along with the information of resources required to complete the task are processed by the iDSS which provides suggestions on prioritisation and optimal series of actions.

4.1.3 Evaluation Scenario ES3: Supporting Incident Detection & Recognition Operations

The scope of this evaluation scenario is to monitor the real working environment under normal or extraordinary conditions in order to detect and recognize incidents that may happen or have just occurred. In this case, a number of different sensors will be utilized,

such as depth sensors, thermal cameras, wearable localization sensors, etc. depending on the use case and the incidents that the SatisFactory is interested in.

4.1.3.1 ES3.1: Supporting Cell Temperature Incidents During Jar Formation

In this evaluation scenario, the cell temperature of the batteries during the jar formation process, which is a critical parameter, is going to be monitored utilizing thermal infrared sensors. If the temperature of the batteries' cells is below or upper the limit, then the jar formation process fails. A successful support is the one that **automatically monitors** the jar formation process, **on-the-fly checks** the real-life data at real-time, **detects potential problems** and **send alert** to specified users (employees responsible for this process).

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to address automatic malfunctions of the cells' temperature during the jar formation by detecting it and inform on-time the end-user, so as to make the necessary actions.

As part of the impact assessment analysis, the evaluation process will take into account both functional and non-functional requirements, since the optimal operation of the system will affect the on-time problem notification to the end-user, the timely mitigation actions, the accuracy (versus to corresponding manual operation) and the saved man hours and effort. Thus, a number of evaluation tests are going to be performed to this end as they described at Annex IV.

4.1.3.2 ES3.2: Recognizing Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor

In this evaluation scenario, the human movements in the shop-floor are going to be monitored, in order to detect and recognize incidents where humans are involved. **Incidents** like human falls, collisions, etc. will be **detected** either proactive or reactive. In any case, the end-users are going to be on-time informed (**send alerts** or **warnings**), for their timely mitigation actions. Furthermore, the system will provide/ distribute safe **optimized paths** to the workers for specific zones and hours so as to minimize the frequency of the incidents.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the scenario is to address automatic detection of the incidents that involve humans, so as to make the necessary actions. Optimal paths are going to be provided to the end-users.

Therefore, the main perspective of this evaluation scenario is to address user satisfaction and acceptance related to the issues concerning incidents, such as the on-time end-user notification, the timely mitigation actions in case of an incident, the number of proactive incidents that are prevented, the quality of the suggested paths, the number of incidents occurred on the suggested paths, etc. Thus, a number of evaluation tests are going to be performed to this end as they described at Annex IV.

4.1.4 Evaluation Scenario ES4: Offering “On-the-Job” Training Services

One assumption in Satisfactory is that the AR technologies (and part of related data) that applies in the assistance to the worker during its normal work (i.e. mounting activities and verify the results), can be the same used during the “on-the-job” training activities.

Many studies proved that assembly applications can benefit substantially from the improved memorization attainable via AR and, the improved memorization can shorten the training time of new employees. Enhancement of long-term memory is also a strong positive factor in the understanding and retention of assembly or repair sequences, procedures and other information.

4.1.4.1 ES4.1 Training environment set-up

The approach will be very similar to the set-up of the environment for the guidance during the Mounting phase when the AR supporting tool is set-up.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the scenario is to address the creation of the environment for support to the worker during the mounting activity. The objective of the evaluation will be to verify the ability to support the trainee through effective multimodal HMI. In particular, main issues addressed are:

- Flexibility in describing the specific training procedures in the various selected BSC;
- Flexibility to easily change the description of such procedures for improving the effectiveness of the training by introducing specific and / or critical situations;
- Existence of full support to the description of procedures based on conditional constructs, as well as on pre-conditions to test or implement in order to safely perform a specific procedure;
- Ability to manage the many types of content to the basis of the description of the training procedures (e.g. Documents, Pictures, Videos, CAD models, etc.) and automatically create new ones in order to enrich the information content provided to the trainee (e.g. 3D animations, audio clips, video clips, etc.);
- Possibility of the solutions used in describing the training procedures, to make automatic part of such description, based on the capture on-the-job-specific data (e.g. Data from motion capture, object recognition, sensor / device-based, etc.)

4.1.4.2 ES4.2 Training support – Execution

The execution stage regards the support to the worker during the on-the job activity. The guidance will be contextualized with the action.

Addressed requirements

Main requirements in this ES are:

- The ability to monitor and control (to the extent made available by the state of the technology) the procedures performed by the trainee, in order to immediately report or made available for subsequent analysis, anomalies, errors and / or specific triggered events;
- The ability to raise additional information to the main ones proposed by the system;

- Ability of the trainee to talk to his supervisor and/or instructors, in order to receive help and / or specific directions to follow.

4.1.4.3 ES4.3 Training support – Data Analysis

In this phase, the results obtained during the execution are analysed. The tool will create comparisons with previously accumulated data and will provide input for the individual or trainee groups statistical analysis.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process addresses:

- Ability to process efficiently the data accumulated during the training, whether they are related to the execution time, the events generated by the system in case of anomalies and errors, voluntarily by the operator generated events (e.g. interruption);
- Ability to present the accumulated data and those derived effectively, focusing on visual representations for easy reference.

4.1.5 Evaluation Scenario ES5: Gamification and Collaboration Tools Usage

The scope of this scenario is to evaluate how much SatisFactory tools increase the satisfaction of workers. This is evaluated on the basis of two aspects: Collaboration and Gamification. The aim of the collaboration tool is to improve the social collaboration between workers and as a consequence to result in better satisfaction. The aim of the gamification tool is to motivate unpopular tasks better and as a consequence, to decrease dissatisfaction.

4.1.5.1 ES5.1: Gamification Tools Usage

In this evaluation scenario, workers can collect points for performing certain tasks. These can be unpopular action, like washing the hands in order to clean them from lead before having a break or going to canteen. But also for accepted actions like the submission of a suggestion for improvement points can be generated (cf. 4.1.5.2). The cumulative points of the whole group are publicly displayed with the goal to beat the group result of the former day (win streak approach). At the same time, each worker can access his individual points on which basis he can achieve better avatars, badges or company rewards. A successful support is the one that increases the number of performed unpopular actions and that increases the overall worker satisfaction.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to check whether worker satisfaction is improved with regard to unpopular tasks. These are all tasks which are considered as being annoying, for example, because they reduce the time for breaks.

Particular requirements for unpopular tasks have been identified with regards to dealing with risks, dangers and emergencies in general (Requirement SAFA-156), with washing hands to clean them from lead every time the shopfloor is left in particular (Requirement SAFA-87) and with the training of new production processes (Requirement SAFA-80). Also, especially younger generation people have been identified as target group (Requirement SAFA-62). An identified main driver for satisfaction at work is self-determination. This includes that people should be encouraged instead of forced for conducting unpopular actions. Another identified driver is to see the own success and contribution to a team result. Finally, a safe environment and co-workers who show their awareness of safety issues is a driver for worker satisfaction.

To conclude, two kinds of evaluation tests are performed for this. Firstly, it is checked whether the number of performed unpopular actions has increased. Secondly, the workers' user experience with the system is assessed. This is described in Annex IV.

4.1.5.2 ES5.2: Collaboration Tools Usage

This scenario evaluates whether the collaboration between workers and managers can be improved by installing a support tool for suggestions for improvement process. Workers can submit suggestions for improvement (e.g. process improvements, wellbeing), which are sent to a decider and the decider's decision and justification is returned. The advantage of such a system in comparison to a paper-based version is that meeting the process worker – decider – worker is ensured. A successful support is the one that increases the satisfaction of workers with the suggestions for improvement system.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to check whether worker satisfaction is improved with regard to the suggestions for improvement system. This is one paradigm of how the social collaboration between workers (shopfloor workers and managers) can be improved.

Several requirements for suggestions for improvement system have been identified. First of all, having a process for suggestions for improvement was considered valuable at all places, no matter if it already existed or not (Requirement SAFA-105). Then, in current systems, it was criticized that the submitter often does not get feedback of what happened to his suggestions, which leads to demotivation (Requirement SAFA-146). Finally, there is the need from the decider side to discuss the issues with co-workers (Requirement SAFA-97). Identified drivers for satisfaction at work, which are supported with the suggestions for improvement system are carriage of responsibility, being valued, diversity in work tasks, breaking monotony in mind, being trusted, seeing the own contribution to the work and the ability to help others. Thus, the workers' user experience with the system is assessed as described in Annex IV.

4.2 EVALUATION PLANNING

In the previous sections the methodological approach was described, as well as the pilot sites and the Generalised Evaluation Scenarios that will make use of the presented criteria and Key Performance Indicators. In this Section we answer to the question: "How is this evaluation plan going to be implemented?"

First of all, the planning procedure gave the focus and working groups a chance to better examine and evaluate their day-to-day activities, in terms of horizontal interconnections with other processes and operations, definition of drivers and decision making factors and departments, as well as expectations from the shop floor level regarding the features of the tools made available to them. This first step was the preparation process for the system evaluation. It is noted that this is the first step of the procedure and that two iterations will follow, which will allow for amelioration and tuning.

The second step within this effort is actually the collection of feedback from the workers and the decision makers, which will also be completed in three iterations, as described below. In order to achieve that, dedicated workshops will be organised and specific tools will be used for the collection of data. The plan foresees two data collections at each shop floor; one after the first iteration of the deployment and another after the completion of the demonstrators.

4.2.1 Evaluation Workshops

The scope of the workshops is to inform the involved personnel that will coordinate the data collection from the three shop floors in the adopted approach and to demonstrate the usage of the tools to be used. These workshops will be in the form of webinars. It is imperative that the objectives and the message behind this effort pass through, in order to reach the required engagement. Dedicated meetings with individual end users may also follow, in order to provide more information and details if needed. It is noted that the involved partners will

support the end users throughout the process and additional guidance will be provided before each workshop.

The procedure is planned as follows:

- First, the T5.2 will present the tools and train the representatives of the end users that will coordinate the data collection from the three shop floors.
- The next step in the deployment of the evaluation is that the trained representatives will organise information sessions, either in the form of briefing of smaller teams or as collective info-sessions. In these sessions:
 - o the overall approach of the SatisFactory framework will be presented,
 - o the scope and goal of the evaluation procedure will be communicated and
 - o the participants will be reminded Business Scenarios that they are being involved.
 - o Moreover, the Workers' Questionnaires will be presented to the corresponding personnel, as well as the
 - o the Decision Makers' Questionnaires and the
 - o the Impact Check List respectively.
- Afterwards, and within a week from the information sessions, the data will be collected, if not simultaneously.
- The data will then be analysed by the involved partners,
- conclusions will be drawn and
- feedback will be provided to the partners and development teams affected by the drawn results.

The three Workshops have been planned as follows.

4.2.1.1 1st Evaluation Workshop (M15-16)

The 1st Workshop is tied to *T5.3 Deployment of the Industry lab use case*, whose first iteration runs in the period M14-M16. Representatives from all the shop floors will participate, to get an insight on the methodology and approach. It is planned to take place in the period end of M15 to beginning of M16, i.e. mid-March to mid-April 2016. The instruments/tools have been already developed (cf. Section 4.3.2) and their presentation during the Workshop will be the only activity related to *T5.2 Evaluation Methodology and Plans*.

The aforementioned timing has been selected, so that the deployment at the CErTH/CPERI shop floor will have progressed enough that the involved personnel will be able to provide initial feedback on the SatisFactory tools used on site. The representatives of the Industrial pilot demonstrators will take part in the 1st Workshop, mainly as observers, in order to follow the first implementation at the Industrial pilot, but they will also provide feedback on the applicability of the procedure to their shop floors and any tuning that may be required.

The results will be analysed and they will be shared with the partners involved in the technical workpackages, as they will provide useful insight on the actual end users point of view and may lead to modifications in the development of the SatisFactory tools. Their analysis of the results will also serve in the improvement of the instruments that will be employed in the following Workshops.

The actual information sessions will be conducted near the end of M16, when the preparation and the initial deployment will reach to its completion at CERTH/CPERI.

4.2.1.2 2nd Evaluation Workshop (M23-M24)

The 2nd Workshop is tied to the deployment at all shop floors serving as demonstrators in the SatisFactory project (*T5.3 Deployment of the Industry lab use case* and *T5.4 Industrial Pilot Demonstrators*). It is planned to take place in the period end of M23 to beginning of M24, i.e. mid-November to mid-December 2016. On one hand, the implementation at the Industrial Lab running M22-M25 will be approaching to its completion and on the other hand implementation at the Industrial Pilots will have just started, as the first iteration runs M22-M27.

Taking into consideration the revisited Business Scenarios and capitalising on the experience gained in the Industrial Lab deployment, the evaluation tools will be revisited to adapt to the latest information made available. Moreover, in cooperation with *T5.1 Preparation and Component Integration to shopfloor* and *T5.5 Evaluation, Results Consolidation and Lessons Learned* the KPIs will also be considered.

The associated information sessions do not need to be conducted simultaneously at the shop floors. They will most probably be concluded sometime until the end of M25 at the Industrial Lab and until the end of M26 at the Industrial Pilots, but this remains to be revisited. The exact dates will be decided based on the availability of the developed tools, the application at the shop floors, the level of realisation of the Business Scenarios and the availability of the involved personnel that will be required to take part in the evaluation procedure.

4.2.1.3 3rd Evaluation Workshop (M31-M32)

The 3rd and last Workshop is tied to the implementation at the two Industrial Pilots (*T5.4 Industrial Pilot Demonstrators*), namely COMAU and SUNLIGHT. The second and last iteration of the deployment will run through M30-M35. The last iteration of *T5.2 Evaluation Methodology and Plans* runs M31-M32 and this is when the Workshop will be organised. It will capitalise on the knowledge gained from the completion of the deployment at the Industrial Lab (M22-M25) and the evaluation results from the 2nd Evaluation Workshop, as well as on the first deployment at the Industrial Workshops (M22-M27). This experience will be also coupled with the results from the technical workpackages (WP1-WP4) which conclude until M30.

Thus, the evaluation tools will be revisited to account for all the changes made, the latest information available and the form of the SatisFactory framework. The aforementioned feedback will be exploited and the findings will be translated into the Evaluation Scenarios that will be presented in the 3rd Workshop, where all end users will participate. The representatives of the Industrial Lab demonstrator will take part to share their experiences to the representatives from the Industrial Pilots and to provide feedback on the applicability of the procedure, any problems encountered and solutions they adopted. The participants from COMAU and SUNLIGHT will be involved in the realisation of the evaluation information session that will follow. Again, these sessions do not need to run simultaneously, but according to each partner's availability and schedule. However, they will need to be

completed within *T5.5 Evaluation, Results Consolidation and Lessons Learned* (M34-M36) and the results will be part of *D5.5 Final System Evaluation Report* (M36).

4.2.2 Instruments

The evaluation procedure will make use of the Evaluation Scenarios and Sub-scenarios which are linked to the Evaluation Tests, which in turn embrace and contain specific KPIs. This approach has been adopted in order to ensure the uniform collection of data that will allow the evaluation of the project objectives, as well as to meet the evaluation objectives.

Moreover, there is the aspect of evaluating the value of the results, as they will be appreciated by the workers and the decision makers, coupled with the sense of the overall impact of SatisFactory. For this part, we will make use of Questionnaires which are collective and associated to specific BSC, ET and ES. Two forms of them have been developed and they will be used (and revisited if needed); the one is dedicated to the workers at the shop floor and the other to the decision makers involved in the respective procedure.

For assessing the overall impact of the SatisFactory framework in a more generic way, an Impact Check List has been produced and will be used for both levels of involvement (workers and decision makers).

The dedicated instruments developed are presented in Annexes I-IV. In Annex I, a set of standard questionnaires is provided, as well as the SatisFactory hybrid questionnaires, dedicated to the assessment of the evaluation tests by the workers. The same goes for Annex II, where a first generic approach is presented, followed by the dedicated SatisFactory questionnaires for the decision makers. Moreover, in Annex III the two Impact Check List are presented (one for the workers and one for the decision makers and other stakeholders), which will be used in all shop floors during the second data collection, towards the completion of the second iteration of implementations. Finally, in Annex IV the exact Evaluation Tests are analysed. The Questionnaires and the Impact Check Lists will be also made available in Greek and Italian, to facilitate their usage at the pilot sites.

CONCLUSIONS

The current deliverable aims at describing the evaluation framework and its realisation plan with the use of evaluation scenarios and provides the methodological framework for the assessment of the SatisFactory platform during the pilot realisation and therefore the guidelines for effective execution of the pilot scenarios. The evaluation objectives, along with the methodological framework served as the base for five Evaluation Scenarios which have been analysed along with the process for the system evaluation in terms of performance and user experience from the end user point of view. The steps that each assessment method would follow and the measurement tools that would be used in each case have been also defined in specific evaluation tests.

The criteria used for the evaluation framework are:

- Usability
- Knowledge integration
- Perception of working experience
- User acceptance
- Impact of SatisFactory

This document outlines the first approach to the assessment and the associated tools which will be revisited in the next T5.2 iterations (e.g. definition of indicators (metrics), data collection tools, implementation of evaluation scenarios).

In order to perform the overall evaluation of SatisFactory, questionnaires have been prepared aiming at different target groups; workers and decision-makers, as well as an overall impact check list. These tools will be used for 2 data collections at each shop floor, in 3 different time periods for the 3 end users involved in the project. Prior to the data collections the Evaluation Workshops will be organised, as well as the following Information Sessions. The experience that will be gained from the application to the Industrial Lab will serve as the basis for the amelioration of the tools.

The feedback from the shop floors will be iteratively assessed, in order to improve functionalities, features and to detect at an early stage of the strong and weak points, aiming always at increasing worker satisfaction, safety and well-being.

REFERENCES

Brooke, J. SUS-A quick and dirty usability scale. *Usability Evaluation in Industry*, pp. 189-194. 1996.

D1.1 User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines

D1.2 Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description

D2.1 SatisFactory System Architecture

Doumeingts G., Clave F. and Ducq Y. “ECOGRAI – A method to design and to implement Performane Measurement Systems for industrial organizations — Concepts and application to the Maintenance function”, *Benchmarking — Theory and Practice*, pp 350-368, Springer US, 1995

Hassenzahl, M. The effect of perceived hedonic quality on product appealingness. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 13(4): pp. 481-499. 2001.

ISO, *ISO 9241-110:2006 Ergonomics of human-system interaction – Part 110: Dialogue Principles*. International Organization for Standardization, 2006

ISO, *ISO 9241-210:2010 Ergonomics of human-system interaction – Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems*. International Organization for Standardization, 2010.

Lobna K., Mourninr B. and Hichem K. Using the ECOGRAI Method for Performance Evaluation in Maintenance Process, *International Conference on Advanced Logistics and Transport (ICALT)*, pp. 382-387, 2013

Nielsen, J. *Usability Engineering*. Morgan Kaufmann, 1994.

Pavlisca, P. Choosing the Right Metrics for User Experience (2014)
<http://www.uxmatters.com/mt/archives/2014/06/choosing-the-right-metrics-for-user-experience.php>

Ramesh, B. and Jarke, M. Toward Reference Models for Requirements Traceability. *IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng.*, 27(1): pp. 58-93, 2001.

Rauschenberger, M., Schrepp, M., Cota, M., Olschner, S., and Thomaschewski, J. Efficient measurement of the user experience of interactive products. How to use the user experience questionnaire (UEQ). Example: Spanish language version. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Multimedia*, 2(1): pp. 39-45, 2013.

Sauro, J. Measuring usability with the system usability scale. (2011)
<http://www.measuringusability.com/sus.php>

ANNEXE I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR WORKERS

SYSTEM USABILITY SCALE

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1	2	3	4	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	1	2	3	4	5
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1	2	3	4	5
4. I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	1	2	3	4	5
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1	2	3	4	5
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	1	2	3	4	5
7. I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	1	2	3	4	5
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	1	2	3	4	5
9. I felt very confident using the system	1	2	3	4	5
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	1	2	3	4	5

ATTRAKDIFF

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

human	<input type="radio"/>	technical						
isolating	<input type="radio"/>	connective						
pleasant	<input type="radio"/>	unpleasant						
inventive	<input type="radio"/>	conventional						
simple	<input type="radio"/>	complicated						
professional	<input type="radio"/>	unprofessional						
ugly	<input type="radio"/>	attractive						
practical	<input type="radio"/>	impractical						
likeable	<input type="radio"/>	disagreeable						
cumbersome	<input type="radio"/>	straightforward						

1/3 cancel next

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

stylish	<input type="radio"/>	tacky						
predictable	<input type="radio"/>	unpredictable						
cheap	<input type="radio"/>	premium						
alienating	<input type="radio"/>	integrating						
brings me closer to people	<input type="radio"/>	separates me from people						
unpresentable	<input type="radio"/>	presentable						
rejecting	<input type="radio"/>	inviting						
unimaginative	<input type="radio"/>	creative						
good	<input type="radio"/>	bad						

2/3 cancel next

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

confusing	<input type="radio"/>	clearly structured						
repelling	<input type="radio"/>	appealing						
bold	<input type="radio"/>	cautious						
innovative	<input type="radio"/>	conservative						
dull	<input type="radio"/>	captivating						
undemanding	<input type="radio"/>	challenging						
motivating	<input type="radio"/>	discouraging						
novel	<input type="radio"/>	ordinary						
unruly	<input type="radio"/>	manageable						

3/3 cancel next

UEQ – USER EXPERIENCE QUESTIONNAIRE

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
annoying	<input type="radio"/>	enjoyable	1						
not understandable	<input type="radio"/>	understandable	2						
creative	<input type="radio"/>	dull	3						
easy to learn	<input type="radio"/>	difficult to learn	4						
valuable	<input type="radio"/>	inferior	5						
boring	<input type="radio"/>	exciting	6						
not interesting	<input type="radio"/>	interesting	7						
unpredictable	<input type="radio"/>	predictable	8						
fast	<input type="radio"/>	slow	9						
inventive	<input type="radio"/>	conventional	10						
obstructive	<input type="radio"/>	supportive	11						
good	<input type="radio"/>	bad	12						
complicated	<input type="radio"/>	easy	13						
unlikable	<input type="radio"/>	pleasing	14						
usual	<input type="radio"/>	leading edge	15						
unpleasant	<input type="radio"/>	pleasant	16						
secure	<input type="radio"/>	not secure	17						
motivating	<input type="radio"/>	demotivating	18						
meets expectations	<input type="radio"/>	does not meet expectations	19						
inefficient	<input type="radio"/>	efficient	20						
clear	<input type="radio"/>	confusing	21						
impractical	<input type="radio"/>	practical	22						
organized	<input type="radio"/>	cluttered	23						
attractive	<input type="radio"/>	unattractive	24						
friendly	<input type="radio"/>	unfriendly	25						
conservative	<input type="radio"/>	innovative	26						

The **Satisfactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS
(WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
16 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
17 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 WE3	I have used the AR tools					
16 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
17 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
18 UA3	I think that AR platform successfully provides access to data/information					
19 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
16 WE1	The SatisFactory platform demonstrates safety and ergonomomy procedures					
17 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
18 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
19 OI3	The system fails frequently					
20 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U9	The framework provides a variety of visualisations					
13 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
14 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
15 WE1	The SatisFactory platform demonstrates safety and ergonomoy procedures					
16 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
17 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
13 U5	I have successfully used the suggestion platform and it is likely that I will reuse it					
14 U10	I feel more motivated and playful in my workplace due to the usage of the platform					
15 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
16 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
17 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
18 UA4	I submit more than 3 suggestions per year to the suggestion platform					
19 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
20 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET6.1 MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 U8	SatisFactory provides straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 WE5	The SatisFactory tools enable continuous monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 KI6	The identification of patterns of workers' movement is successful					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
12 KI3	The average time for training procedures is reduced					
13 KI11	The AR tools of SatisFactory provide efficient information					
14 WE2	The on-the-job-training platform is an improvement to the existing system and the sessions are useful for knowledge and skills enrichment					
15 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 WE8	The SatisFactory tools are able to provide complete and reliable training					
18 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
19 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U10	I feel more motivated and playful in my workplace due to the usage of the platform					
12 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
13 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
14 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
15 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
16 UA10	I think that gamification tools increase the attractiveness of the shop floors					
17 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

ANNEXE II: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DECISION MAKERS

- 1) How do you consider the time required for the development of a new application?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 2) How do you consider the time spent from departments not directly involved in the development and the setting up of an application?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 3) How do you consider the direct cost sustained for the acquiring of specific hardware devices for workers?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 4) How do you consider the indirect costs related to the creation and the taking care of an optimal working site, as required for the trial (installation of cameras and additional lighting point, toolset, RFID and antennas,..)?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 5) How do you consider the indirect cost related to the maintenance and the taking care of the wearable personal workers' devices (clean, protected, ..)?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 6) How do you consider the obtained percentage of reuse of the AR applications?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 7) How seems the Application integrated in the rest of the processes?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

- 8) How do you consider the adequateness of the software in order to preserve the privacy of workers?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

- 9) How do you consider the adequateness of the installed systems in order to preserve the safety of workers?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

- 10) As far as concerns with the objectives of reducing errors, what is the percentage of initial objectives reached with the trial?

A value ranging from 0% to 100%

- 11) As far as concerns with the objective of reducing the cost of maintenance, what is the percentage of initial objectives reached with the trial?

A value ranging from 0% to 100%

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
16 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
17 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
18 OI6	The failures of the system are critical					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 KI11	The AR tools of SatisFactory provide efficient information					
16 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
17 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
18 UA3	I think that AR platform successfully provides access to data/information					
19 UA7	The Standard Operating Procedures required in the pilot test are transformed into AR tools					
20 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
13 U8	SatisFactory provides straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status					
14 U9	The framework provides a variety of visualisations					
15 KI5	The SatisFactory platform reinforces collaboration on the shop floor					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
12 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
16 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
17 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI6	The failures of the system are critical					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
13 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
14 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
15 KI5	The SatisFactory platform reinforces collaboration on the shop floor					
16 KI8	Suggestions submitted to the SatisFactory platform are accepted					
17 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
18 UA5	I use the collaboration platform more than 3 times per year					
19 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET6.2 MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 WE5	The SatisFactory tools enable continuous monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras					
15 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
16 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
17 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 KI6	The identification of patterns of workers' movement is successful					
15 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
16 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
17 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI3	The average time for training procedures is reduced					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 KI9	I think the necessary time for the preparation of training procedures is reduced using the SatisFactory tools					
16 KI10	SatisFactory tools helps reduce training costs					
17 WE2	The on-the-job-training platform is an improvement to the existing system and the sessions are useful for knowledge and skills enrichment					
18 WE8	The SatisFactory tools are able to provide complete and reliable training					
19 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

QUESTIONNAIRE ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
12 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
13 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
14 UA10	I think that gamification tools increase the attractiveness of the shop floors					
15 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
16 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
17 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
18 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

ANNEXE III: IMPACT CHECK LIST

Checklist for Impact Analysis	
Overview	<p>Impact Analysis is being done because a change is occurring at the shop floor level in terms of work management and introduction of new devices.</p> <p>The checklist below can be used when evaluating the impact of SatisFactory in each Pilot Site.</p>
Evaluation Criteria	<p>The following criteria should be met (when applicable):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Knowledge integration • Perception of working experience • User acceptance <p>Impact of SatisFactory</p>
End-Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worker • Decision maker
Exit Criteria	<p>The following criteria should be met after using this checklist.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Impact Analysis is complete and shows no undesired impacts are caused by the introduction of new tools • Evaluation plans have been updated to verify the evolution of the shop floor performances

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

IMPACT CHECK LIST 1 (WORKERS)

PILOT SITE:					
#	Criteria	Yes	No	N/A	Remarks
Usability					
	<i>The SF platform provides appropriate visualisation and incident management tools.</i>				
	<i>The required information (resources, data and guidelines) is available in real-time.</i>				
	<i>The information provided through the SF platform is appropriate and easy to understand.</i>				
Knowledge Integration					
	<i>The provided training methods, content and materials improve the process of knowledge and skills enrichment required to perform tasks.</i>				
	<i>The SF platform promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing between the workers at the shop floor.</i>				
	<i>The shop floor knowledge is managed and presented through the SF platform in an attractive way.</i>				
Perception of working experience					
	<i>The use of AR tools in daily activities is attractive and improves the working experience on the shop-floor.</i>				
	<i>The SF on-the-job training system is innovative and the visualisations offered facilitate memorisation.</i>				
	<i>The introduced collaboration and gamification elements empower the team spirit.</i>				
User Acceptance					
	<i>The use of the SF tools helps performing daily operations more efficiently and with less mental effort.</i>				

SATISFACTORY

	<i>The use of the new tools and technologies reduces fatigue and discomfort and improves the quality of work.</i>				
	<i>The introduction of the SF framework is well received and the users are confident to employ the proposed technologies.</i>				
Impact of SatisFactory					
	<i>The developed tools offer a user friendly assistance and training to ordinary and extra-ordinary operations in the shop floor in real time.</i>				
	<i>The adoption of the proposed tools and technologies does not require considerable additional workload.</i>				
	<i>The SF framework capitalises the knowledge and experience created on the shop floor and supports a more collaborative and attractive workplace.</i>				

The **SatisFactory** project: a collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing SATISfaction and working experience in smart FACTORY environments

IMPACT CHECK LIST 2 (DECISION MAKERS)

PILOT SITE:					
#	Criteria	Yes	No	N/A	Remarks
Usability					
	<i>The SF platform provides appropriate visualisation, incident management and decision support components and techniques for the users (e.g. process operators and supervisors).</i>				
	<i>The required information (resources, data and guidelines) is available to the workers in real-time and facilitates timely completion of the necessary tasks.</i>				
	<i>The task of migrating daily activities to be done through the SF platform requires a lot of effort.</i>				
Knowledge Integration					
	<i>The developed platform delivers different views of information depending on the organisational level and localisation of the end-user (i.e. user-specific information).</i>				
	<i>The training platform provides faster and more effective training, helping knowledge and skills enrichment.</i>				
	<i>The relevant shop floor knowledge is managed and analysed through the SF platform.</i>				
Perception of working experience					
	<i>The use of AR tools in daily activities is attractive, time-saving and improves safety on the shop-floor.</i>				
	<i>The SF on-the-job training system is innovative and the visualisations offered facilitate memorisation. The transition from the existing training environment to the SF on-the-job training system using semantic technologies, AR devices and tools leads to faster and more effective training on the shop floor.</i>				

SATISFACTORY

	<i>The introduced collaboration and gamification elements support team building.</i>				
User Acceptance					
	<i>The introduced SF tools are suitable form the point of view of ergonomoy and safety.</i>				
	<i>It is easy to use the SF platform for scheduling, re-adaptation and co-ordination of activities at the shop floor.</i>				
	<i>The introduction of the SF framework is well received and the users are willing to employ the proposed technologies.</i>				
Impact of SatisFactory					
	<i>The use of the SF platform enhances problem solving and decision making capabilities and improves productivity.</i>				
	<i>The SF concepts and tools help balance the workload of employees, ensure safety of workers on the shop floor and reduce work-related stress.</i>				
	<i>The proposed system contributes to the transfiguration of traditional industrial environments into attractive and safe workplaces.</i>				

ANNEX IV: EVALUATION TESTS

EVALUATION TEST ET1: AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET1	Version	1.0
Test Name	Manual assembly operations		
Created by	ATL/REGOLA	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to motivate the interaction between the workers, to increase in the usage and easy access to the knowledge repository of the company, and to timely provide data and instructions to the shop floor. The workers will receive information such as mechanical drawings, connections diagrams, assembly instructions, inspection instructions, packing instructions at the respective working stations through conveniently located HMIs. To this end, the toolkit will be prompted to operate when an assembly operation is required (8 hours per day maximum).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES1.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor/Foreman: He/She is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation. • Workers: They are responsible for the normal operation of the assembly process.
Satisfactory End	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HMI and smart assembly station digital andon: used to

SATISFACTORY

Users utilized	Tools display the assembly procedure and iterate through steps; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information; • CIDEM: used to store the assembly requiring requests; • Gesture and Recognition Manager: used to interact with the assembly instructions, require assistance, propagate information about the progress status and monitor presence. • Collaboration Platform: used to share knowledge among the workers and problem solving tips • HMI & mobile applications: used to project the notifications and set of information required to perform the task.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not Applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify all the necessary technical information • Retrieve all the necessary technical information from an information system; • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Collaboration among the workers for the successful completion of the task.
Test Procedure	The steps to follow by the tester are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's SOP for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches; • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the automated support; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the suitability of information provided.
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U2, U7, U11, KI1, KI2, KI12, WE6, WE7, UA8, UA9, OI2, OI3, OI6, OI7, OI8, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Both Production Supervisor and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the equipment. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the emergency level, the location of the malfunction etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

EVALUATION TEST ET2: AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET2	Version	1.0
Test Name	AR Supported assembly operations		
Created by	REGOLA/GLASSUP	Last updated by	
Date created	19/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The main objective of this evaluation test is to reduce the errors and to increase the effectiveness in the manual assembly of a mechanical system. An additional objective is to reduce the stress of the worker and to create a positive feeling to participate into a user community having novel and advanced ways for social interaction and communication.</p> <p>We can distinguish three distinct phases in the evaluation process:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) creation of the “guidance” program, starting from the SOPs and all the necessary basic information. That includes CAD models, descriptions assembly procedures and other multimedia material (eg. 3D animations, audio clips, text messages, 3D models, etc); b) execution, using the virtual and the augmented reality, of the guidance program during the assembly phases; c) collection, during the mounting operating, of all essential Information requested for the subsequent “analytics” phase; the main scope here is to check the goodness of the performed work and make comparisons between different sessions executed in different times.
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES1.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor / Foreman: He / She is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation. • Assembly Procedures Designer: represents the figures dedicated to the task of extracting all the data and

SATISFACTORY

	<p>information related to the assembly procedures selected in the associated ESs (as well as UCS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content Creation Designer: represents the figure dedicated to the task of enriching the original data (e.g. CAD, description of procedures) producing new content (e.g. animations, videos) • AR Assembly Designer Procedures: represents the figure (only potentially coincident with the precedent) responsible for the collection and derivation of all the data useful for the description of a procedure for AR Tools • CAD designer: the person dedicated to the task of extracting data (as 2D/3D models) involved in the assembly procedures • Worker: is the figure to whom the whole development is mainly addressed. He/she is the person dedicated to the assembly procedures. • Data Analyser: the figure dedicated to analyse the information/data collected in the course of the assembly procedures (e.g. Running times, successes events)
<p>SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR Tools used for the fruition and support the conduct of assembly procedures; • Data Analytics Tools, used for the analysis of information / data collection at runtime; • HMI and smart assembly station digital station: used to display the assembly procedures and iterate through steps; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information; • CIDEM: used to store the assembly operating procedures; • Gesture and Recognition Manager: used to interact with the assembly instructions, require assistance, propagated information about the progress status and presence monitor.
<p>Precondition(s) / Input</p>	<p>Availability of the following items:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) CAD models of the component involved in the procedures 2) description of the assembly procedures 3) environment-related requirements
<p>Postcondition(s) / Output</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieve all the necessary technical information from an information system; • Creation of the guidance program; • Visualisation of the necessary technical information; • Provision of actors with the necessary information.

SATISFACTORY

Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the Following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Verification and validation of the operational environment preparation;• Installation of all the useful tools on different platforms;• Verification and validation of the provided basic content;• Verification and validation of the derived content;• Verification and validation of the assembly procedures implemented with the augmented reality tool (RA Creation Tool use);• Check the performance "driven" the bonding procedures (AR Visualization Tool use);• Verification of information/data collected at runtime, using tools of Data Analytics;• Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's SOP for a period of time (e.g., two months);• Comparison between the results from Both existing and satisfactory approaches;• Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the automated support.
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U2, U3, U11, KI1, KI7, KI11, WE3, WE4, WE6, WE7, UA3, UA7, UA9, OI7, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	The workers will be able to receive support for assembly operations via AR tools. The Supervisor will be able to monitor the status of the progress of the operation.

SATISFACTORY

EVALUATION TEST ET3: CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET3	Version	1.0
Test Name	Corrective maintenance, re-adaptation and HR workload balancing		
Created by	ATL/ISMB	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to allow the team on the shop floor to respond in case of equipment failure and to resume production in the optimal operating conditions. In this case the complete toolkit to be installed is comprised by the iDSS, re-adaptation, CMMS and HR workload balancing components.</p> <p>The iDSS will be fed with alarms and data analytics from real shop floor data, in order to detect an incident. In case of an equipment failure, the iDSS will suggest actions and interact with the CMMS creating a Work Order, the re-adaptation tool will highlight the occurring malfunction to the supervisor and the HR workload balancing tool will evaluate who is available to respond.</p> <p>To this end, the toolkit will continuously operate when the specific production line is in operating condition (depending on operating hours in each shop floor).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES2.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor/manager: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. • Technicians of Maintenance team (electrical, process, control): They are responsible for the normal operation of the process.

SATISFACTORY

SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iDSS: used to detect and report the abnormal operation of the process; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; • CIDEM: used to store the alarm events; • HR toolkit & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/ alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	<p>Existing of faulty or degraded resistance.</p>
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the process; • Identify equipment failure; • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Replacement of faulty equipment with minimum downtime of the operation.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check for identification of the malfunction of the resistance either from the process operator or from the automation (SCADA) system for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches; • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the SatisFactory one; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	<p>U2, U3, U6, U8, U9, U11, KI1, KI2, KI5, KI12, WE1, WE6, WE9, UA2, UA6, UA9, OI1, OI3, OI7, OI8</p>
User Experience Evaluation	<p>Both Process Manager and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the equipment. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the emergency level, the location of the malfunction etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.</p>

EVALUATION TEST ET4: PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET4	Version	1.0
Test Name	Preventive maintenance, re-adaptation and HR workload balancing		
Created by	ATL/ISMB	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to allow the team on the shop floor to organise their preventive maintenance activities in an efficient and more automated way. The complete toolkit to be installed is comprised by the iDSS, re-adaptation, CMMS and HR workload balancing components. The iDSS will be fed with the preventive maintenance schedule from the CMMS and will suggest actions. Considering the workers availability using the HR workload balancing tool it will suggest actions and interact with the CMMS. The re-adaptation tool will allow the Process Manager to review the shop floor status and respond. To this end, the toolkit will continuously operate when the specific production line is in operating condition (depending on the conditions on each shop floor).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES2.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor/manager: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. • Technicians of Maintenance team (electrical, process, control): They are responsible for the normal operation of the process.
Satisfactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iDSS: used to prioritise suggested actions based on predictive maintenance schedules; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute data and SOP;

SATISFACTORY

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIDEM: used to store SOP and the related information; • HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Existing of faulty or degraded resistance.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the process; • Recognise the need to implement preventive maintenance action; • Readaptation of HR • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Depending on trigger, startup or reconfigure the process.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check from the process manager for identification of need for preventive maintenance activities for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches (no duplicate preventive maintenance programs, correct rescheduling based on time or units etc.); • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the SatisFactory one; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U6, U7, U9, U11, KI1, KI12, WE1, WE7, UA1, UA2, U9, UA11, OI3, OI4, OI6, OI8, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	The Process Manager will be able to have a clear view and organise the preventive maintenance schedule and actions required. In case of a need to implement preventive maintenance at a different time due to the experiments or the equipment status, he/she will be notified about the priority level, the required resources etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

SATISFACTORY

EVALUATION TEST ET5: COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET5	Version	1.0
Test Name	Satisfaction with Suggestions for Improvement Platform		
Created by	FIT	Last updated by	
Date created	11/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation is to assess the satisfaction of shopfloor workers and deciders of the suggestions for improvement platform through user experience evaluation. A frontend where suggestions can be entered, viewed and rated will be installed at the shopfloor. They are being submitted to the respective decider and the feedback (accepted, accepted with modification or rejected with justification) can be requested by the submitter at the frontend again. This is expected to lead to a better knowledge sharing as process knowledge and best practices are distributed within the company.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES5.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decider: He/She has to decide whether a suggestion is accepted (will be put into practice), accepted with modification or rejected with justification. There are different deciders for different suggestion categories Worker: Submit, view and rate suggestions and request feedback of suggestions submitted by himself
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration Tools: receive, distribute and manage suggestions for improvement; Middleware: connect different parts of the system; CIDEM: define data exchange format; HMI & mobile applications: worker and decider frontends.

SATISFACTORY

Precondition(s) / Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Suggestions for Improvement• Ratings• Decider feedback
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process ensured• Knowledge shared• User satisfaction achieved
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Installation of the backend;• Installation of the network infrastructure;• Installation of the frontends;• Introduction of the system to workers and deciders;• Running the system for 6 months;• User experience assessment of the users
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U2, U3, U5, U6, U7, U10, KI4, KI5, KI8, WE7, WE9, UA2, UA4, UA5, UA8, OI2, OI5
User Experience Evaluation	Standard user experience questionnaires as in Annexe I have to be filled out by the system's end users in order to assess the user experience

EVALUATION TEST ET6: MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (DETECTION OF EITHER MANUALLY DRIVEN OR REAL INCIDENTS)

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET6	Version	1.0
Test Name	Monitor Jar Formation Operation (detection of either manually driven or real incidents)		
Created by	CERTH	Last updated by	
Date created	05/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to monitor real jar formation operation under real-life conditions. In this case, infrared cameras monitoring the cells of the batteries are going to be installed. The infrared streaming will be real-time processed, in order to detect potential incident during the process. In case of an accident, an alert event is going to be sent timely at the end-users. To this end, the toolkit will continuously (24 hours per day) monitor the cells' temperature distinguishing the different status (e.g. idle times, start of the process, normal process, incident, etc.) of the operation and send notifications (e.g. alerts) in case of an incident.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES3.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. • Workers: They are responsible for the normal operation of the jar formation process.
Satisfactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident detection engine: used to detect and report the abnormal operation of the jar formation process; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; • CIDEM: used to store the alarm events;

SATISFACTORY

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Continuously monitor the Jar Platforms;• Identify any unusual temperature variation above or below the normal;• Timely notification to the involved actors.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Installation of the infrared (thermal) cameras;• Installation of the corresponding toolkit;• Concurrent manual check of the cells' temperature for a period of time (e.g. three months);• Comparison between the results extracting from both manual (existing one) and automatic approaches;• Gradually replacement of the manual operation with the automatic one;• Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U4, U8, KI2, WE5, WE6, UA1, UA6, UA12, OI1, OI4, OI5, OI12
User Experience Evaluation	Both Facility Manager and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the Jar formation process. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the status of the cells, the emergency level, the location of the batteries, etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

EVALUATION TEST ET7: RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET7	Version	1.0
Test Name	Recognition of Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor		
Created by	CERTH	Last updated by	
Date created	05/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	1 week		
Iterations	6		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to monitor and track the workers in the shop-floor detecting incidents like human falls, collisions, etc. utilizing depth and wearable sensors. In a case of an incident, then the workers will be notified by an alarm message at their HMIs or their mobile devices or even using the central alarm system. Furthermore, the system will be able to detect proactive incidents, which means to predict incidents before they occur. In any case, the alarm message will be accompanied with an emergency level providing information about the status and the type of the incident. Furthermore, optimal routes inside the shop-floors will be provided to the end-users in case of an incident, so as workers avoid extra incidents or dangerous areas in the shop-floor.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES3.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shop-floor related actors: All actors that will work in the shop-floor and more specific at the monitored areas.
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident detection engine: used to detect and report incidents; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; • CIDEM: used to store the alarm events; • HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/

	alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the shop-floor and the workers; • Identify any incidents; • Timely notification to the actors; • Optimal paths in case of proactive and reactive incidents.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the depth and wearable sensors at the shop-floor; • Installation of the corresponding toolkit; • Initiation of the toolkit; • “Simulation” of incidents by actors in the shop-floor very close to the real-conditions; • Evaluation of the usability and the acceptability; • Leave the system for a period of time to test it under real-life shop-floor conditions; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notifications mechanism.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U4, U7, KI2, KI6, WE6, UA1, UA6, UA12, OI1, OI2, OI4, OI5
User Experience Evaluation	All actors in the shop-floor will be notified when an incident occurred or is going to be occurred through their HMIs and their mobile devices. Optimal paths are going to be provided as well. In all cases, actors evaluate the performance of the system, its usability, ease to use features, its visualizations and above all its impact to their everyday working life in the shop-floor.

EVALUATION TEST ET8: ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET8	Version	1.0
Test Name	On-the-job training in assembly operations		
Created by	REGOLA/ATL	Last updated by	
Date created	19/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of the evaluation test is the reduction in the time and costs of the training. Another objective is the reduction of time and errors occurred in the assembly of systems that are rarely in the year/working time for a workers (less than 10 times per year).</p> <p>We can distinguish two sessions with different objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. create "conditional-based training program" where conditions can however be predetermined in order to easily set the same training conditions to one or more trainee 2. empower communication trainee and trainer
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES4.1, ES4.2, ES4.3
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor/Foreman: He/she is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation • Assembly Procedures Training Designer: represents the figures dedicated to the task of extracting all the data and information related to the training assembly procedures selected in the associated ESs (as well as UCS) • Content Creation Designer: represents the figure dedicated to the task of enriching the original data (e.g. CAD, description of procedures) producing new content (e.g. animations, videos) • AR Assembly Procedures Training Designer: represents the figure (only potentially coincident with the precedent) responsible for the collection and derivation of all the data

SATISFACTORY

	<p>useful for the description of a procedure for AR Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAD designer: the person dedicated to the task of extracting data (as 2D/3D models) involved in the assembly procedures • Trainer: is the person in charge of training, directly involved during the training sessions (based on the explicit request of Satisfactory to allow two-way communication between trainee / trainer) • Trainee: is the figure to whom the whole training program development is mainly addressed. He/she is the person dedicated to the training assembly procedures. • Data analyser (usually the trainer): the figure dedicated to analyse the information/data collected in the course of the training assembly procedures (e.g. running times, successes events)
<p>Satisfactory End Users Tools utilized</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR Training Tools used for the fruition and support the conduct of training assembly procedures; • Data Analytics Tools, used for the analysis of information / data collection at runtime; • HMI and smart assembly station digital station: used both to display the assembly procedures and iterate through steps, and to allow the bidirectional communication between trainer and trainee; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information.
<p>Precondition(s) / Input</p>	<p>Availability of the following items:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) CAD models of the component involved in the procedures 2) description of the training assembly procedures 3) environment-related requirements
<p>Postcondition(s) / Output</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformation of SOPs to AR tools; • Provision of actors with the necessary information; • Training of workers; • Collaboration among the workers, the trainers and the trainees for successful completion of the training.
<p>Test Procedure</p>	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification and validation of the operational environment preparation; • Installation of all the useful tools on different platforms; • Verification and validation of the provided basic content • Verification and validation of the derived content; • Verification and validation of the training assembly

	<p>procedures implemented with the augmented reality tool (AR Creation Tool use);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check the performance "driven" the bonding procedures (AR Visualization Tool use); • Verification of information / data collected at runtime, using tools of Data Analytics; • Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's OP for a period of time (e.g., two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and satisfactory approaches.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U11, KI3, KI7, KI9, KI10, KI11, WE2, WE4, WE6, WE8, UA12, OI2, OI5, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Both Production Supervisor and Workers will be able to evaluate the Experience on the basis of the reports automatically created during the execution of the training sessions.

EVALUATION TEST ET9: GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET9	Version	1.0
Test Name	Gamification Platform		
Created by	FIT	Last updated by	
Date created	11/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	The objective of this evaluation is to assess the satisfaction of shopfloor workers of the gamification platform through user experience evaluation. A platform will be installed to which other components can commit points for certain actions. Group points are displayed at a public display and individual points can be requested over a private approach. The aim is motivate workers to perform the actions, especially unpopular actions.
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES5.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External components: Commit user actions to the gamification platform • Worker: Perform the actual actions • Managers: Grant rewards
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification Platform: receive, provide and manage points, badges, avatars, tasks, players and games; • Middleware: connect different parts of the system; • CIDEM: define data exchange format; • Digital an-don and mobile applications: private and public frontends.
Precondition(s) / Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reported worker actions from external components
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of performed unpopular tasks increased

SATISFACTORY

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• User satisfaction achieved
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Installation of the backend;• Installation of the network infrastructure;• Installation of the frontends;• Connection to other components;• Collection of number of unpopular tasks for 3 months without the system• Introduction of the system to workers and deciders;• Running the system for 3 months;• Collection of number of unpopular tasks with the system• User experience assessment of the users
Evaluation Metrics	U10, KI4, WE9, UA1, UA8, UA10, UA11, OI2, OI4, OI5, OI7, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Standard user experience questionnaires as in Annexe I have to be filled out by the system's end users in order to assess the user experience